

An Roinn Oideachais
Department of Education

Institiúid Oideachais
Institute of Education

Pedagogical Strategies, Approaches and Methodologies to Support Literacy in the Primary School

A Review of Research

**Prepared by: Eithne Kennedy, Tara Concannon-Gibney and
Bernadette Dywer, Institute of Education, Dublin City University, for
the Department of Education**

Author Note

Geraldine French <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7075-038x>

Gillian Lake <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4315-1971>

Suggested Citation

Kennedy, E, Concannon-Gibney, T. & Dwyer, B. (2022). *Pedagogical strategies, approaches and methodologies to support literacy in the primary school: A review of research*. Department of Education (Ireland).

Summary of Findings: Pedagogical Strategies, Approaches and Methodologies to Support Literacy in the Primary School

Oral Language Development and Integrated Literacy Instruction

Oral expressive language skills play a key supportive role in literacy development (Shiel et al., 2021; Snow, 2016; Dobinson & Dockrell, 2021) and in supporting learning across the curriculum (Alexander, 2013; Shiel et al., 2012). The quality of oral language has also been found to impact on social, emotional, and mental health at school (Benner et al., 2002; APPG, 2021), and to contribute to success in later life (Schoon et al., 2010) as it opens access to further education and employment. It is also key to engaged and agentic citizenship (APPG, 2021; Allington & McGill Franzen, 2021).

Oral language skills can be effectively developed within authentic literacy contexts (e.g., interactive book reading, literature discussion, writing processes and genres, inquiry-based learning, disciplinary literacy, critical literacy) through engagement in purposeful activities and should be supported by explicit intentional teaching linked to students' stage of development (Dobinson & Dockrell, 2021; EEF, 2021; Murphy et al., 2009; Wixson et al., 2020). Embedding oral language within such contexts supports children in developing a metalanguage to express their thoughts and responses while simultaneously supporting the development of key literacy skills (e.g. vocabulary, comprehension, composition). For example, in discussing and justifying the linguistic choices made in their writing, children develop knowledge of language components and how their word choices shape and alter meaning (Myhill & Watson, 2014). Additionally, literature discussions with strong student voice and agency have been found to be highly effective when a critical analytic stance is emphasised and a focus on higher-order comprehension skills is maintained. They are of most benefit to middle and lower- achieving students and have been linked to gains in reading comprehension (Murphy et al, 2009).

Integrating the forms of language within lessons has strong support in the research literature (Graham, 2020; Graham et al. 2018a, 2018b). Balancing attention to reading and writing and embedding meaningful oral language into both is more effective than teaching these skills separately or as isolated decontextualized activities. Combining reading and writing instruction benefits skill development in both reading (word reading, fluency, vocabulary, comprehension) and writing (grammar, spelling, punctuation, expression across genres).

Opportunities for independent reading and writing also enhance literacy development and should complement explicit systematic classroom instruction in key literacy skills (Jouhar & Rupley, 2021). The success of integrated instruction is mediated by the level of professional development provided to teachers to plan and implement such instruction and the degree to which interventions are matched to curriculum and learners' current stage of development (Dobinson & Dockrell, 2021; EEF, 2021, Murphy et al., 2009).

Children need to experience a comprehensive, integrated approach to literacy instruction that is balanced in nature and which incorporates explicit teaching of a range of literacy skills including phonological awareness, phonics, morphology, vocabulary, oral reading fluency, comprehension, spelling, handwriting, and writing processes and genres and that gives due attention to the affective dimensions of literacy (Wixson et al., 2020; Graham et al., 2018a;

Reynolds et al, 2011; Kennedy et al., 2012; Eurydice Report, 2011). It is important to note that the term ‘balanced literacy’ has vastly varying interpretations depending on jurisdiction. For example, in the US in recent times, it has become a politicised and contested term which has reignited the ‘reading wars’, as the term is interpreted by some to mean insufficient attention is paid to the explicit and systematic teaching of key foundational early literacy skills necessary for successful reading. In the UK, on the other hand, Wyse and Bradbury (2022) have called for a more balanced approach to literacy instruction given the over-emphasis on synthetic phonics approaches to word reading in UK curricula and policy. Based on our reviews of the literature, in this paper, we interpret balanced literacy to mean: balanced in terms of attention to and systematic explicit teaching of constrained (e.g. phonics, letter knowledge, punctuation) and unconstrained (vocabulary, comprehension composition) skills according to children’s assessed needs and stage of development; balanced in access to a wide variety of genres and ‘texts’ in reading and writing; balanced in terms of formative and summative assessment practices; and balanced in terms of attention to oral language, reading and writing recognising the reciprocal relationship and supportive processes existing between the forms of language. This means that a teacher must attend to both the explicit and systematic teaching of code-based skills (e.g. phonics) with the provision of meaningful opportunities to apply these skills when reading connected texts (connected texts are meaningful texts with multiple related sentences characterised by a coherent and cohesive structure) and when creating texts in a variety of genres and disciplines).

Development of Component Reading Skills

Phonological awareness and alphabet knowledge must be explicitly taught in a systematic manner in the early years of school in accordance with assessed needs, including the segmentation of syllables, onset- rimes, and phonemes in spoken words and how these units of sound correspond to letters (Eurydice Report, 2011; Foorman et al., 2016; Invernizzi & Tortorelli, 2013; Reynolds et al., 2011; Kennedy et al., 2012). Interventions that used teacher read-alouds of storybooks have been found to enhance children’s phonological awareness (Swanson et al., 2011). Instruction in phonemic awareness is most effective when combined with letter manipulation and when children are taught in small groups for a limited time (20 hours) (Foorman et al, 2016; Invernizzi & Tortorelli, 2013; Reynolds et al., 2011; NICHD, 2000). Additional instruction should be directly linked to the teaching of phonics and spelling (Invernizzi & Tortorelli, 2013).

Nevo et al’s (2018) interactive storybook-reading intervention programme, which was delivered by kindergarten teachers to 30 Hebrew-speaking kindergarten children, showed improvements for the intervention group in vocabulary, morphology, phonological awareness and print concepts on language and print-concept skills. Nicolopoulou et al’s (2015) study in the USA facilitated children acting out and sharing/telling their own stories. Repeated sharing of children’s own stories with groups increased narrative comprehension and some emergent literacy skills (phonological awareness, syllable and word awareness). Thus, the way the book is shared and the activities that follow are important supports for language development and must be developmentally appropriate.

It is important that teachers adopt a systematic approach to phonics instruction for younger readers that emphasises sound-spelling patterns, morphological elements of words and the interrelation between phonology, morphology and etymology (Ehri, 2020; Eurydice, 2011;

Reynolds et al., 2011; Torgerson et al., 2019). Invented spelling can be a useful tool in developing phonemic awareness, which is essential in learning to decode and encode (Ouellette & Sénéchal, 2017). As highlighted in Kennedy et al. (2012, citing Gentry, 2000; Ehri, 1993), the process of *writing* words (encoding) and the process of *reading* words (decoding) draws upon the same underlying base of word knowledge. The more pupils know about the structure of words (including their spelling) the more efficient and fluent their reading will be. Thus, ‘spelling knowledge can be viewed as a driving force behind efficient reading as well as efficient writing’ (Kennedy et al., 2012, p.67). Phonics should form part of a total reading programme that is balanced with instruction that focuses on aspects of reading for meaning (Bowers, 2020; Eurydice, 2011; Reynolds et al., 2011; Wyse & Bradbury, 2022). Struggling readers can benefit from experiencing small group phonics instruction (Eurydice, 2011). Morphology instruction has also been found to be beneficial in supporting literacy achievement, as it can lead to enhanced performance in relation to decoding, phonological awareness, spelling and vocabulary (Goodwin & Ahn, 2013; Sedgwick & Stothard, 2018).

There should be a sustained emphasis on the development of vocabulary throughout primary school (Cregan, 2019). It is helpful if instruction incorporates direct instruction and implicit exposure to new vocabulary, including academic vocabulary (Foorman et al., 2016; Hattie, 2009; Reynolds et al., 2011). Children need to have multiple encounters with target vocabulary across different contexts and will benefit from explicit teaching that incorporates contextual analysis, morphemic analysis and semantic analysis (Hairrell et al., 2011; Sedgwick & Stothard, 2018; Wright & Cervetti, 2016). Multi-sensory and multi-modal techniques can help to anchor word knowledge (Lawson-Adams & Dickinson, 2020; Rowe et al., 2013; Tellier, 2008). It may be helpful to teach pupils multiple and flexible strategies for solving word meanings in order to enhance their comprehension (Wright & Cervetti, 2016).

Interactive book reading has been found to aid the development of vocabulary through high-quality discussion, extended vocabulary activities and repeated reading of well-chosen texts (Swanson et al., 2011; Wasik et al., 2016). These lessons can be further enhanced if instruction incorporates phonics, morphological awareness and phonological and orthographic tasks in follow-up activities (Sedgwick & Stothard, 2018). The use of challenging, inferential and extra-textual talk during shared reading lessons with young children has been found to be particularly beneficial (Dickinson & Porche, 2011; Zucker et al., 2013).

Oral reading fluency can be enhanced through repeated readings that are guided by the teacher (Hudson et al., 2020; Rasinski et al., 2009; Reynolds et al., 2011). Approaches that incorporate repeated readings include paired reading, assisted reading, phrase reading, radio reading, ‘the oral recitation lesson’ (ORL), ‘fluency development lessons’ (FDLs), ‘fluency orientated reading instruction’ (FORI), and Fast Start (Eurydice, 2011; Kennedy et al. 2012; Nichols et al., 2009; Rasinski et al., 2009). Instructional level texts are deemed useful in enabling students to practise accurate decoding and encoding, and rereading the texts can build oral reading fluency, particularly in intervention settings (Foorman et al., 2016). Children need to read connected text every day to become fluent readers. Oral reading fluency interventions have also been found to enhance reading comprehension achievement (Hudson et al., 2020).

Good readers orchestrate a repertoire of strategies as they read and these strategies can be taught in classrooms to increase reading comprehension (Clinton et al., 2020; Davoudi &

Sadeghi, 2015; Elleman, 2017). Teachers should teach students a range of comprehension strategies that will help them construct meaning from text while concurrently teaching and developing metacognition and supporting students to become independent self-regulated readers. Explicit or formal instruction of reading comprehension strategies by the teacher involves demonstrating, modelling, and guiding the reader to use these strategies independently when reading (Davis, 2013; Reynolds, 2017). Teachers should choose texts that support their teaching goals and improve reading comprehension (Shanahan et al., 2010). Students construct meaning from text when taught the structure of both narrative and informational (including expository) texts (Ray & Meyer, 2020; Shanahan et al., 2010). In addition, there are strong reciprocal relationships between the prior or background knowledge a reader brings to the text and the reader's ability to construct a coherent model when comprehending a text (Fielding & Pearson, 1994). Readers draw on prior or background knowledge, in an active metacognitive fashion, to make connections, determine importance, make inferences, monitor and repair comprehension, and derive summaries. Research suggests (Smith et al., 2021) that low skilled readers who have strong prior or background knowledge of a subject can compensate, to some extent, for poor reading skills. This is dependent on the coherence and cohesion of the text structure.

Students with limited vocabulary knowledge can encounter difficulties with reading comprehension because vocabulary is an essential enabler of reading comprehension development. Integrating literacy and content area instruction enhances both vocabulary and comprehension while concurrently developing content area knowledge throughout the primary school system (Hwang et al, 2021).

Development of Component Writing Skills

Writing is a complex problem-solving process (McCutchen, Teske, & Bankston, 2008) and depends, at least in part, on the writer's understanding of and experience with the writing process and with the various skills involved in composing a text. The capacity to write well is fundamental to success in school and supports future learning of more complex knowledge, which in turn supports individuals in discovering and reaching their potential in life (Graham, 2019; Kennedy & Shiel, 2019). In line with UNESCO (2021), Camacho et al., (2021, p.214) consider writing to be 'a key skill in the twenty-first century and a gateway to lifelong learning, employment, and social inclusion. Writing also provides the means for 'personal reflection, thought, creativity, creation of meaning and exchange of ideas, as well as a complement to other modes of communication in a world of multimodal texts' (Patino et al., 2020, p. 494). Writing development is influenced by the 'affordances of classrooms which can either constrain and hinder it or propel it forward' (Kennedy & Shiel, 2022, p.1). A common theme across research studies on writing is the provision of sufficient daily time for students to write using a range of modes (written, multimodal, digital) in a range of genres for real purposes and audiences (Graham et al., 2012a, 2012b; Graham 2019). Daily time to write on self-chosen topics within authentic contexts and opportunities to share writing with an audience is linked to writer motivation, creativity, agency and identity (Vaughn 2020; Camacho et al., 2021; Limpo & Graham, 2020). It is necessary for teachers to provide systematic incremental explicit instruction on the crafts, processes and conventions of writing if children's writing quality and accuracy is to be optimised (Graham et al. 2012a, 2012b; McMaster et al. 2018; Koster et al. 2015; Graham et al., 2015; Graham 2019; Kennedy et al. 2012; Kennedy & Shiel, 2019).

Process-based approaches to writing have been found to be effective in supporting students as writers across multiple genres (Graves, 1994; Graham & Sandmel, 2011). They are most effective when explicit mini-lessons in genre-specific crafts, processes and conventions of writing are taught using self-regulated strategy instruction and include goal setting which in turn supports development of children's metacognition (McMaster et al. 2018; Koster et al. 2015; Graham et al. 2012a, 2012b; Graham 2019). It is important that teaching is adequately balanced between the lower and higher-order dimensions of writing as research indicates that higher-order dimensions are often neglected (Graham et al., 2012a; Kennedy et al., 2012; Kennedy & Shiel, 2019).

A key feature of process-based approaches to writing is writer support while writing, which includes teacher feedback in conferences and opportunities for students to collaborate with peers. Teacher modelling of how to give and receive feedback has been found to support students in peer and self- assessment and to impact positively on the quality of writing (Slavin et al., 2019; Kennedy & Shiel, 2019; Graham et al., 2011; Graham et al., 2012a; Graham et al., 2015).

There are conflicting findings on the role of grammar in writing pedagogy and its potential to impact on writing quality. Its potential to impact writing quality depends on how it is conceptualised and presented in curricula, the extent to which it is taught in isolation 'as an arbiter of accuracy' (Myhill & Watson, 2014, p.45) or if taught within the context of authentic writing where it can be utilised as a design tool for communicating. Early meta-analyses (cited in Graham et al., 2012a) concluded that grammar teaching in isolation has little or no effect on students' writing (Hillocks and Smith, 1991) or a negative effect on it (Braddock et al., 1963). More recently, Graham & Perrin (2007, cited in Graham 2012a) and Koster et al. (2015) also found negative effects of systematic teaching of the parts of speech and structure of sentences on writing quality. However, when conceptualised as a design tool and attention paid to the lexical, syntactical and rhetorical dimensions within authentic writing contexts, it has been found to be effective in raising the quality of writing (Myhill & Watson 2014; Kennedy & Shiel, 2022).

Spelling is an integral part of the orthographic knowledge that underlies efficient, automatic generation of words during writing (encoding), and efficient, automatic perception of words during reading (Kennedy et al., 2012; Ouellette & Sénéchal, 2017). Including formal systematic and explicit spelling instruction as part of a balanced literacy framework has been found to support students as writers and frees up the cognitive resources needed for the higher-order processes of writing (Graham & Santangelo, 2014; McMaster 2018; Kent & Wanzek, 2016). As noted above, providing opportunities for young children to compose using invented spelling has been found to not only benefit writing processes but has also been identified as playing a causal role in later proficient reading development (Ouellette & Sénéchal, 2017; Kennedy et al. 2012) and supports children in acquiring the alphabetic principle.

Like spelling, explicit attention to handwriting has been shown to impact positively on writing development and quality (McMaster et al., 2018; Fancher et al., 2018) and writer self-efficacy as it frees up cognitive resources, allowing the writer to concentrate on ideas, language choice, genre and expression (Santangelo & Graham, 2016; Feng et al., 2019). A range of interventions have been found to be effective in improving handwriting skills in children up to 9th grade (equivalent to Junior Cycle in Ireland). In designing an intervention, writing should be assessed for legibility, fluency, accuracy and speed (Patino et al., 2020; Graham et al., 2012; Dwyer et al., 2022). Handwriting practice should be distributed over time (e.g. 10 minutes daily)

and 10 hours is sufficient for most students to master handwriting (Santangelo & Graham, 2016; Limpo & Graham 2020).

Research highlights the important role of handwriting in linking letter names and sounds and has been found to be even more effective than tracing or passively viewing a letter (Fancher et al., 2018). Mayer et al. (2020) note the proliferation of digital writing devices in primary classrooms which increasingly replace handwriting with pencil and paper. Their small-scale study examined differences in literacy skill acquisition at the letter and word level among kindergarten children who received three different approaches to handwriting. Across 7 weeks children were trained with 16 letters by handwriting with (a) a pencil on a sheet of paper; (b) by writing with a stylus on a tablet computer; (c) or by typing letters using a virtual keyboard on a tablet. Results revealed that handwriting with a pencil fostered better acquisition of letter knowledge and improved visuo-spatial skills compared with keyboarding. The pencil and paper and keyboard groups had higher performance in word writing and reading compared with the stylus group. Writing with a stylus on a touchscreen was deemed least satisfactory (perhaps due to greater demands on motor control).

Though learning to touch type is an important life skill and students should have the opportunity to learn it, it should not replace handwriting instruction (Graham et al., 2012a; Feng et al. 2019). While meta-analyses did not examine the optimum age at which children should learn to touch type, in countries where keyboarding skills are indicated in national curricula, they first appear in third grade when children have developed greater manual dexterity and their hands can span the keyboard. For example, the Common Core State Standards in the US, keyboarding appears in the writing standards for third grade students when publishing. By fourth grade, students must “*demonstrate sufficient command of keyboarding skills to type a minimum of one page in a single sitting*” (CCSS, 2016, p. 21) and two pages by fifth grade. Feng et al. (2019) explored the associations between handwriting or keyboarding on writing quality across 19 studies involving students from Kindergarten to adolescence. Findings confirmed previous studies (e.g. Graham et al. (2012a, 2012b); Limpo & Graham, (2020); Kent & Wanzek, (2016) that handwriting fluency is a significant predictor of student performance in relation to writing compositional quality, fluency and substantive quality. Students with better handwriting fluency also had better keyboarding fluency indicating a significant correlation between both operations. In the Irish context, ePIRLS 2016 data suggested that less than half (47%) of Fourth class pupils agreed a lot that they were good at typing (Eevers & Delaney, 2018). Overall, though there are too few studies comparing keyboarding skills with handwriting skills on compositional writing quality (Graham et al. 2012a; Feng et al., 2019, students should be taught to type (Graham et al. 2012a) and third or fourth grade appears to be a good age to build such skills systematically in developmentally appropriate ways (Donika et al., 2018).

Key Role of Motivation and Engagement in Literacy Development

Motivation for reading accounts for variance in reading performance beyond academic or cognitive skills (Toste et al., 2020; Wigfield, Gladstone, Turci, 2016). Teachers should examine ways in which school contexts provide spaces for the development of agency and in turn engagement and motivation (Vaughn et al., 2020). Instructional practices that allow students to construct identities as readers, develop positive dispositions towards reading, that involve and encourage dialogue, critical engagement and privilege student choice in terms of materials and resources should be considered (Vaughn et al., 2020; Murphy et al., 2009; EEF, 2021). Gender differences are noted by Wigfield et al. (2016) with girls more positively motivated to read than

boys. The authors suggest that educators adopt measures to improve male students' competence beliefs and the value placed on reading. These include providing informative feedback; setting challenging but achievable tasks; the promotion of active learning goals, and the creation of regular opportunities for students to promote what they are reading through book talks (Barber et al., 2018).

Writing development is influenced by writer motivation, engagement and agency (Camacho et al. 2021; Vaughn et al., 2020). These affective dimensions of writing can be supported by providing students with the kinds of experiences e.g. social persuasion, vicarious and mastery experiences that build their confidence and success with writing (Bandura, 1995; Kennedy & Shiel, 2019). Creating conditions for an engaged community of writers to develop in the classroom supports students to view themselves as writers (Graham et al., 2012a; Kennedy & Shiel, 2019).

As highlighted earlier, oral expressive language skills play a key supportive role in literacy development (EEF, 2021; Shiel et al., 2012). They are strongly correlated with levels of print exposure (Mol & Bus, 2011) and are important in cultivating positive dispositions towards literacy. They can be developed within authentic literacy contexts (e.g. interactive book reading, literature discussion, writing processes, disciplinary literacy and cross curricular contexts (Kennedy et al., 2012; Alexander, 2013; Shiel et al., 2012; Dobinson & Dockrell; Snow 2016). Book discussions provide a motivating context for students to articulate text interpretation in responding to culturally responsive and engaging texts linked to their interests and stage of development. High-quality literature discussions which emphasise a critical analytic stance and maintain a focus on higher-order comprehension skills can support strong student voice and agency (Murphy et al., 2009; Soter et al., 2008). In writing, providing an audience for authors through daily share sessions enhances engagement as authors receive timely feedback from peers and teachers. Additionally, when oral language permeates daily share sessions, it cultivates positive writer identities and enhances students' understanding of writing as a social and communicative act (Graham et al., 2012a; Kennedy & Shiel, 2019)

Recommendations

Pillar 1: Enabling Parents & Communities

See French et al., (2022)

Pillar 2: Teachers and ECEC Professional Development and Learning

- Teachers should be provided with extensive professional development to support them in developing the content and pedagogical content knowledge required for effective literacy instruction. It should support them in balancing attention to oral language, reading and writing in ways that are research-informed, matched to learners' stage of development and linked appropriately to curriculum (Dobinson & Dockrell, 2021; EEF, 2021, Murphy et al., 2009); see King et al., 2022; Giblin et al., 2022) for further literacy-specific CPD recommendations.
- Professional development in writing should ensure that teachers experience the writing strategies they will employ (Slavin et al., 2019); Graham, 2019); such experiences are critical to influencing teachers' beliefs about writing, their dispositions toward writing and writer identity which it is argued increases the likelihood that they will write, enjoy writing, see the value of writing and teaching it (Graham, 2019).

Pillar 3: School and ECEC leadership

- School leaders should be provided with extensive professional development in relation to research-informed balanced literacy instruction in order to support them in leading teachers in the development of an effective school-wide balanced literacy framework (Graham, 2019; Eurydice Report, 2011; Kennedy et al., 2012); see King et al., 2022; Giblin et al., 2022 for further literacy-specific recommendations.
- Professional development should support all relevant stakeholders in developing a *positive identity as a writer* and an understanding of how best to cultivate an engaged school-wide community of writers (Graham, 2019; Kennedy & Shiel, 2019)

Pillar 4: Curriculum and the learning experience

Balanced Literacy Instruction

- Teachers should adopt a comprehensive, integrated approach to literacy instruction that is balanced in nature. As there are varying interpretation of the the term balanced literacy (see section above), we interpret balanced in this paper to mean: balanced in terms of attention to and systematic explicit and intentional teaching of constrained (e.g. phonics, letter knowledge) and unconstrained skills (e.g. Vocabulary, comprehension, composition) tailored to children's assessed needs and stage of development; balanced in providing access to a wide variety of genres and 'texts' in reading and writing; balanced in terms of formative and summative assessment practices and balanced in terms of attention to oral language, reading and writing recognising the reciprocal relationship and mutually supportive processes between them. (Bradbury & Wyse, 2022; Graham et al., 2018a; Reynolds et al, 2011; Kennedy et al., 2012; Eurydice Report, 2011;).This means that a teacher must attend to both the explicit and systematic teaching of code-based skills (e.g. phonics) with the provision of meaningful opportunities to apply these skills when reading connected texts (connected texts are meaningful texts with multiple related sentences characterised by a coherent and cohesive structure) and when creating texts in a variety of modes, genres and disciplines).

- Teachers should integrate oral language, reading and writing within literacy instruction, rather than teaching them in isolation from each other given the reciprocal relationship between the forms of language (Graham et al., 2018a, 2018b; Graham, 2020; Eurydice Report, 2011; Kennedy et al., 2012; Dockrell & Dobinson, 2021).
- Teachers should provide opportunities for independent reading and writing in addition to explicit literacy instruction (Jouhar & Rupley, 2021).
- The time allocation for literacy should be given careful consideration in future policy and curriculum developments to ensure sufficient time is allocated for children to develop key literacy skills within a balanced approach to literacy (Graham et al., 2012a; Shanahan, 2010; Kennedy et al., 2012; Graham, 2019, 2020).

Oral Language Development

- Teachers should integrate oral language into meaningful contexts such as interactive book reading, literature discussions, content areas across the curriculum, writing process and writing genres approaches (Dobinson & Dockrell, 2021; Graham et al., 2018a, 2018b; Dwyer et al., 2022). To impact on expressive language skills, teaching must be purposeful and intentional (APPG, 2021; EEF, 2021).
- Teachers should adopt a dialogic approach to literature study and emphasise higher-order comprehension skills and critical appraisal of texts. (EEF, 2021; Murphy et al., 2009).
- Teachers should use embed oral language development into writing contexts and use opportunities within these contexts to scaffold language interaction and build greater sophistication in oral language over time.

Reading Dispositions, Agency, Motivation and Engagement

- Teachers should examine ways in which school contexts provide spaces for the development of agency and in turn engagement and motivation given that motivation for reading accounts for variance in reading performance beyond academic or cognitive skills (Toste et al., 2020; Wigfield et al. 2016). Instructional practices that allow students to construct identities as readers, develop positive dispositions towards reading, involve and encourage dialogue, critical engagement and privilege student choice in terms of materials and resources should be considered (Vaughn et al., 2020).
- To address gender differences in motivation to read between males and females, educators should adopt measures to improve the value placed on reading by male students. Teachers should provide consistent informative feedback on effective reading strategies; set challenging but achievable tasks; promote active learning goals, such as monitoring understanding through self-questioning; and create regular opportunities for students to promote what they are reading through book talks (Wigfield et al., 2016).

Phonological Awareness

- Phonological and phonemic awareness must be explicitly and systematically taught in the early years of school (Eurydice Report, 2011; Invernizzi & Tortorelli, 2013; Reynolds et al., 2011; Kennedy et al., 2012). Teachers should read storybooks aloud regularly to enhance phonological awareness (Nevo et al., 2018; Swanson et al, 2011). Children should be encouraged to act out, share and tell their own stories as a means of enhancing phonological awareness (Nicolopoulou et al., 2015). Teachers should explicitly teach students to segment syllables, onset-rimes, and phonemes in spoken words. Twenty hours of phonemic

awareness instruction is optimal; instruction should be combined with letter manipulation, taught in small groups, in sessions of approximately 30 minutes duration (Foorman et al, 2016; Invernizzi & Tortorelli, 2013; Reynolds et al., 2011). Further instruction should be directly linked to the teaching of phonics and spelling (Invernizzi & Tortorelli, 2013).

Phonics, Spelling and Morphology

- Phonics should be part of a total reading programme, and balanced with instruction that focuses on aspects of reading for meaning (Bowers, 2020; Eurydice, 2011; Reynolds, Wheldall & Madelaine, 2011).
- Teachers should adopt a systematic approach to phonics instruction for younger readers (Eri, 2020; Eurydice, 2011; Reynolds, Wheldall & Madelaine, 2011; Torgerson et al., 2019) that emphasises sound-spelling patterns, morphological elements of words and the interrelation between phonology, morphology, and etymology. Struggling readers should experience small group phonics instruction (Eurydice, 2011; see also Kennedy & Shiel, 2022; Reynor, 2022).
- Children should experience formal systematic and explicit spelling instruction, given that spelling is an integral part of the orthographic knowledge that underlies efficient, automatic generation of words during writing, and efficient, automatic perception of words during reading; spelling instruction influences reading achievement and frees up the cognitive resources required for higher-order processes of writing (Kennedy et al., 2012; Graham & Santangelo, 2014; McMaster 2018; Kent & Wanzek, 2016)
- Teachers should consider the important role played by invented spelling in learning to decode and encode (Ouellette & Sénéchal, 2017; Kennedy et al., 2012). Children in the early years of primary school should have opportunities to utilise invented spelling as they compose; invented spelling supports phonological and phonemic awareness and has been shown to provide a causal pathway to proficient reading (Ouellette & Sénéchal, 2017).
- Teachers should teach morphology as part of their reading instruction (e.g. identifying, segmenting, and building with morphemes; teaching morphological patterns that support spelling; exploring affix and root meanings and examining compound words) (Goodwin & Ahn, 2013; Sedgwick & Stothard, 2018).

Vocabulary Development

- There should be a sustained emphasis on the development of vocabulary (Cregan, 2019). Vocabulary should be taught both incidentally and directly using multiple methods (Hattie, 2009; Reynolds, Wheldall & Madelaine, 2011) across different contexts (Coyne et al., 2009; Grover, 2017; Nielsen & Friersen, 2012).
- Interactive book reading that involves discussion, extended vocabulary activities and multiple readings of the text should be used to develop children's vocabulary (Swanson et al, 2011; Wasik, Hindman & Snell, 2016). Teachers should use a combination of embedded instruction; where vocabulary is taught in context of a text using child friendly definitions, and extended vocabulary instruction that incorporates phonics, morphological awareness and phonological and orthographic tasks in follow-up activities should occur (Sedgwick & Stothard, 2018). Teachers should use challenging, inferential and extra-textual talk during shared reading lessons with young children to enhance vocabulary development (Dickinson & Porche, 2011; Zucker et al., 2013).
- Graphic organisers should be used when appropriate to support vocabulary learning (Hairrell, Rupley & Simmons, 2011).

- Vocabulary instruction should include a focus on academic language skills (Foorman et al., 2016). Teachers should use multimodal approaches to vocabulary learning (gestures, images and sounds) (Lawson-Adams & Dickinson, 2020; Rowe et al., 2013; Tellier, 2008), particularly when the focus is on academic vocabulary (Townsend, Filippini, Collins, & Biancarosa, 2012).

Fluency Development

- Children need to read connected text every day to become fluent readers (Foorman et al., 2016; Kennedy et al., 2012). Oral reading fluency should be developed through the repeated reading of texts that are guided by the teacher (Hudson et al., 2020; Rasinski et al., 2009; Reynolds, Wheldall & Madelaine, 2011). Approaches that incorporate repeated readings include paired reading, assisted reading, phrase reading, radio reading, ‘the oral recitation lesson’ (ORL), ‘fluency development lessons’ (FDLs), ‘fluency orientated reading instruction’ (FORI), and Fast Start (Eurydice, 2011; Kennedy et al. 2012; Nichols, Rupley & Rasinski, 2009; Rasinski, Homan & Biggs, 2009). Teachers should also use echo reading, choral reading, partner reading and reading with a computerised device to enhance oral reading fluency (Foorman et al., 2016). Teachers should consider the role played by oral reading fluency in developing comprehension (Hudson et al., 2020).

Comprehension Development

- Teachers should teach students a range of comprehension strategies that will help them construct meaning from text while concurrently teaching students to become independent self-regulated readers (Davis, 2013; IES, 2010). Teachers should choose texts that support their teaching goals and improve reading comprehension. Students construct meaning from text when taught the structure of both narrative and informational (including expository) texts (Ray & Meyer, 2011; Shanahan, Callison, Carriere, Duke, et al., 2010).
- Teachers should consider integrating literacy with content area (across the curriculum) instruction to enhance vocabulary, comprehension, writing, oral language and content knowledge (Hwang et al., 2021). This recommendation should be considered in light of the ongoing review of the curriculum at primary and post-primary level.

Writing Motivation, Engagement and Agency

- All children in primary school (JI to 6th) should have daily opportunities to engage in compositional writing for real purposes and audiences in authentic contexts (Graham et al., 2012a, 2012b; Graham 2019). Time is linked to writing motivation and creativity and is a prerequisite for quality instruction and for competency to develop; time should be split between explicit instruction and time for children to actively compose (Graham et al., 2012a; Limpo & Graham 2020; Graham 2019).
- To enhance student agency, engagement and writer identity, students should have ownership over their writing through choice of topic and determination of time spent on a particular topic; (Vaughn 2020; Camacho et al., 2021; Limpo & Graham, 2020).
- Teachers should ensure conditions in classrooms support students’ motivation, engagement and self-efficacy given the link with writing quality (Camacho et al. 2021; Vaughn 2020; This can be accomplished by providing social persuasion, vicarious and mastery experiences that build students’ confidence and success with writing (Limpo et al., 2020; Kennedy & Shiel 2019).

Writing Processes and Writing Genres

- Teachers should adopt a process-based approach to writing and combine it with explicit teaching of strategies for planning, drafting, revising, editing and publishing writing on a regular basis. When teaching these strategies, teachers should combine self-regulated strategy instruction pedagogies (SRSD) and goal setting and also link strategies to the genre form (McMaster et al. 2018; Koster et al. 2015; Graham et al. 2012a, 2012b; Graham 2019).
- Students should be explicitly taught text structures for each genre of writing; Links should be made with reading text structures (Graham et al., 2012b; Koster et al., 2015).
- Teachers should scaffold and support children when engaged in the act of writing (Graham et al., 2012b); Children should be provided with opportunities to collaborate and support each other in writing (Slavin et al., 2019)
- Students should be explicitly taught how to assess their own and others' writing drafts, to give and receive feedback using insights gained from effective writing strategies taught. These need to be modelled by the teacher (Slavin et al., 2019; Graham et al., 2012a; Kennedy & Shiel, 2019). Teachers should also give timely focused and specific feedback to student on their writing quality (Koster et al., 2015; Graham et al., 2011; Graham 2012a; Graham, Hebert & Harris, 2015).
- Instruction should be balanced between the higher-order dimensions of writing and the mechanics of writing (grammar, spelling and punctuation) (Graham et al., 2012a; Kennedy et al., 2012; Kennedy & Shiel, 2019).

Grammar and Writing Instruction

- Grammar should be taught in the context of authentic writing where it can be utilised as a design tool for communicating. Grammar should not be taught through isolated decontextualised activities. Instead, to improve writing quality, teachers should focus on the lexical, syntactical and rhetorical features of language within the context of authentic writing within genres and across the disciplines. Children should be taught to compose syntactically more complex sentences as they develop their writing skills (Myhill & Watson 2014; Koster et al., 2015; Jagaiah et al. 2020). EAL pupils will also benefit from some explicit contextual teaching, though much of their emerging syntactic knowledge will grow from implicit teaching within the context of tasks and teacher feedback (August, McCardle & Shanahan, 2014; Baker et al., 2014; Kang, Sok & Han, 2019).

Handwriting and Touch-Typing

- Teachers should ensure explicit systematic instruction in handwriting to benefit legibility and writing fluency, to improve writing quality (McMaster et al., 2018; Fancher et al., 2018) and influence writer self-efficacy (Santangelo & Graham, 2016; Feng et al., 2019). biweekly to daily lessons lasting 10 to 30 minutes are recommended (Limpo & Graham, 2020).
- In Infants to 3rd class, handwriting practice should be distributed over time (e.g. 10 minutes-20 minutes daily) and older children (4th class up to 3rd Year) should receive between 5-10 hours of age-appropriate instruction (Santangelo & Graham, 2016; Limpo & Graham 2020).
- In teaching beginning handwriting (print or cursive), children should be taught to simultaneously recognise and name a letter, sound it and write it (Fancher et al., 2018). Schwellnus et al., 2012). Writing a letter is more effective than sensori-motor activities such as typing, tracing, passively viewing, and saying the letter name out loud (Fancher et al., 2018).

Teachers should assess handwriting for legibility, speed, fluency and accuracy (Limpo & Graham, 2020)

- Teachers should assess handwriting for legibility, speed, fluency and accuracy (Limpo & Graham, 2020).
- Students should be taught to touch type as a valuable life skill but technology should not replace handwriting instruction which is foundational to writing (Graham et al., 2012a; Feng et al., 2019); students should be taught digital, multimodal and word processing skills (Patino et al., 2020) (See B3 report for digital literacy)
- **Pillar 6: Assessment and evaluation to support learning in literacy and numeracy.**
(see Shiel et al., 2022)

Pedagogical Strategies, Approaches and Methodologies to Support Literacy in the Primary School

Introduction

The overarching question that guided this systematic review of the research was, how can all learners in the primary sector be supported in developing literacy skills within oral language, reading and writing and across the curriculum? We drew on a large volume of systematic reviews and meta-analyses which had been conducted in areas we deemed relevant since 2011. We augmented these with other identified key studies, reports and reviews. The methodology and search strategy is detailed in Appendix A.

Arising from the categorisation above, the following sub-questions were generated and guided our search strategy and report:

1. What systematic reviews or meta-analyses have been conducted that are relevant to the area: Oral language, reading, writing?
2. How can learners in K-6 be supported in developing reading skills within literacy?
3. How can learners in K-6 be supported in developing writing skills within literacy?
4. How can learners in K-6 be supported in developing oral language skills within literacy?

Our report is divided into three parts. The first explores recent research conducted in relation to effective reading instruction. Then, the second section examines how writing skills might be effectively developed in the primary school classroom. Finally, research-based approaches for the integration of oral language skills with reading and writing are discussed.

Effective Reading Instruction in Primary School

Motivation and Reading

In a seminal chapter on motivation and engagement for reading Guthrie and Wigfield (2000) noted that engaged reading is strategic, conceptual, motivated and intentional proposing that engaged readers “co-ordinate their strategies and knowledge (cognition) within a community of literacy (social) in order to fulfil their personal goals, desires, and intentions (motivation)” (p.404). Motivation is a multidimensional construct underpinned by a range of theories (see

Barber, Levush, & Klauda, (2018) for a review). The engaged reader is strategic, has personal goals for reading, is agentic, self-efficacious, interested, self-regulated and has expectations of success. Individual actions are driven by affective, cognitive and behavioural aspects such as, thoughts, beliefs, goals, values and dispositions.

There is growing evidence to suggest that motivation for reading accounts for variance in reading performance beyond academic or cognitive skills (Toste et al., 2020; Wigfield, Gladstone, Turci, 2016). In a meta-analysis conducted by Toste et al. (2020) a moderate relationship between motivation and reading ($r=0.22$) was found. However, although evidence to support the bi-directional nature of the relationship between motivation and reading is offered, findings from the meta-analysis suggest that foundational early reading instruction and early experiences with reading performance is a stronger predictor of later motivation.

Instructional Contexts to Develop Reading Motivation and Engagement

Researchers point to instructional contexts to develop motivation and engagement for reading. Toste et al. (2020) note that the integration of direct skills instruction and motivation might produce “synergistic effects and optimise gains in reading performance over time” (p.446). Vaughn et al., (2020) urge educators to examine ways in which school contexts provide spaces for the development of agency and in turn engagement and motivation. They urge instructional practices that allow students to construct identities as readers, develop positive dispositions towards reading, involve and encourage dialogue and critical engagement and privilege student choice in terms of materials and resources. Gender differences are noted by Wigfield et al. (2016) with girls more positively motivated to read than boys. The authors suggest that educators adopt measures to improve male students’ competence beliefs and the value placed on reading. Barber et al. (2018) note the need for consistent informative feedback on effective reading strategies; the need to set challenging but achievable tasks; the promotion of active learning goals, such as monitoring understanding through self-questioning; and the creation of regular opportunities for students to promote what they are reading through book talks.

Effective Instruction of Reading Components in Primary School

Reynolds, Wheldall and Madelaine’s (2011) review indicated that early reading programmes and interventions should include: direct and explicit instruction in all components:

phonological and phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension. Indeed, the Eurydice Report (2011) recommended a comprehensive, integrated approach to literacy instruction that is balanced in nature (see also Graham et al., 2018). This section will explore these essential elements of reading instruction and make recommendations for research-based effective instruction at primary school level.

Phonological and Phonemic Awareness

Foorman et al.'s (2016) review of current research identifies that teachers should explicitly teach students to segment syllables, onset-rimes, and phonemes in spoken words and how these units of sound correspond to letters. It also suggests that children should be taught the distinctive features of letters so that students can distinguish one letter from another alongside phonological awareness skills. Invernizzi, and Tortorelli (2013) agree that phonological awareness and alphabet knowledge must be explicitly taught, and that children need abundant opportunities to apply these skills (see also Eurydice Report, 2011). Swanson et al. (2011) reported that children's phonological awareness skills were enhanced when teachers read storybooks aloud as part of an intervention program (see also Nevo et al., 2018). While Nicolopoulou et al.'s (2015) study demonstrated the effectiveness of children acting out and sharing/telling their own stories in enhancing phonological awareness.

Reynolds, Wheldall and Madelaine's (2011) review included *The National Reading Panel* (NICHD, 2000) recommendations in relation to phonemic awareness. Phonemic awareness instruction was found to be highly effective in improving children's reading. It is most effective when it features explicit and systematic teaching that links the manipulation of phonemes with the associated letters, and when instruction is limited to the teaching of only one or two phoneme manipulation skills (for example blending and segmenting phonemes). It is most effectively taught in small groups, for sessions of approximately 30 minutes in duration. Research indicates that 20 hours of training time is most effective. The most effective results are achieved when instruction is provided by classroom teachers and other trained professionals rather than by paraprofessionals or through computer programs. Phonemic awareness is most effective when taught in preschool and kindergarten rather than in older grades. Reynolds et al.'s (2011) review also examined Hattie's (2009) *Synthesis of Meta-analyses* related to achievement in reading that recommended that

phonemic awareness should be taught early and should focus mainly on two key aspects, blending and segmentation.

Phonics

Foorman et al.'s (2016) review of current research highlight that children need to be taught to decode words, analyze word parts, and write and recognize words. Teachers should emphasise sound-spelling patterns (e.g. consonant digraphs, vowel teams, r-controlled vowels) and morphological elements of words. Children should be taught how to encode as well as decode so that they can recognize them quickly and use them in their writing. Kennedy et al. (2012) also highlighted the usefulness of invented spelling in developing phonemic awareness and decoding skills (see also Ouellette & Sénéchal, 2017).

Torgerson, Brooks, Gascoine and Higgins' (2019) review recommends systematic phonics instruction for younger readers (see also Ehri, 2020). However, they included the caveat that the evidence is not clear enough to stipulate which phonics approach is best. They also found that there was insufficient evidence to justify a 'phonics only' teaching policy as many of the effective studies within their review had added phonics to whole language approaches. Their review maintained that questions related to phonics 'dosage' remains in terms of the amount or length of instruction. Bowers (2020) found that phonics is important but little or no evidence that systematic phonics is better than standard alternative methods used in schools (unsystematic or a mixed approach). Bowers (2020) recommended that teachers and researchers should consider alternative methods of reading instruction for example emphasising morphology and the interrelation between phonology, morphology, and etymology. Suggate (2016) recommended that preschool and kindergarten interventions should target phonemic awareness alone and decoding skills should be left to Grades 1 and 2 for intervention purposes, which differs from the recommendations found in Reynolds, Wheldall and Madelaine's (2011) review and the National Reading Panel Report (NRP, 2000) which suggests that phonemic awareness training is most effective when combined with alphabetic knowledge and Kennedy et al.'s (2012) recommendation to include invented spelling in phonics instruction which enhances the link between phonemic awareness and letter knowledge. Suggate (2016) also noted the limitations within phonics interventions as their effects did not tend to transfer to non-targeted skills such as comprehension. Therefore, a multi-componential approach to early literacy teaching would be recommended.

Reynolds, Wheldall and Madelaine (2011) included recommendations from *The National Reading Panel* (NICHD, 2000) in their review. The evidence from the NICHD showed that systematic phonics instruction is more effective than either instruction that does not teach phonics systematically or instruction that teaches little or no phonics. Phonics instruction is most effective in kindergarten and year one. Phonic skills contributed to both decoding, spelling and comprehension ability in lower grades but only to decoding, spelling and oral reading in higher grades.

Reynolds, Wheldall and Madelaine (2011) also included criticisms of the NRP's findings about the role and teaching of phonics in studies which re-analysed data (Camilli, Kim, & Vargas, 2008; Camilli et al., 2003; Garan, 2001; Hammill & Swanson, 2006). These analyses revealed smaller effect sizes for a systematic approach over a non-systematic approach ($d = 0.24$) compared to the NRP's findings of $d = 0.41$ and insufficient evidence to say that, in general, students have better results when given phonics instruction in comparison with students given reading instruction without phonics. They also found that phonics instruction efficacy was limited to the improvement of decoding skills and did not necessarily transfer to other reading skills.

Reynolds, Wheldall and Madelaine (2011) included *The National Inquiry into the Teaching of Literacy* (NITL) in their review. It recommended direct systematic instruction in phonics during the early years of schooling, but that phonics should be part of a total reading programme, rather than a goal in itself. It also found that sight word recognition and comprehension of written text are essential and they should be taught explicitly and early in a child's schooling. Reading instruction should be integrated and include phonics, phonemic awareness, fluency, comprehension and vocabulary. They also determined that there is a lack of evidence to support the use of a whole-language approach. However, reading instruction that is code-based should be balanced with instruction that focuses on aspects of reading for meaning (Eurydice, 2011).

The Eurydice Report (2011) highlighted the need for a 'clear programme or plan' (p.32) for phonics rather than 'more sporadic attention' (p.32) as systematic phonics instruction has a positive impact on the reading development of young and struggling readers. It also found that small group instruction in phonics is effective for struggling readers, with some evidence to suggest one-to-one tutoring is most effective.

Morphology in Reading

In Goodwin and Ahn's (2013) metaanalysis of morphological interventions, they found that the largest effects were for decoding, phonological awareness, and morphological knowledge, as this relates to synergistic relationship between morphology and phonology. There were moderate effects for spelling and vocabulary and a lack of overall effect on fluency and reading comprehension as these involve the largest degree of transfer. Their research found that various types of morphological instruction support literacy achievement, (e.g. identifying, segmenting, and building with morphemes; teaching morphological patterns that support spelling; exploring affix and root meanings; examining compound words). Sedgwick and Stothard (2018) found that including morphological awareness tasks in extended instruction improved the effectiveness of vocabulary interventions as morphological awareness is reciprocally related to word knowledge.

Vocabulary Development

Wright and Cervetti's (2017) review highlighted that teaching word meanings supports comprehension of text containing the same target words. They found that instruction emphasizing active processing was more effective than definition- or dictionary-based methods of vocabulary instruction. There was limited evidence that direct teaching of word meanings can improve overall reading comprehension and there was no empirical evidence that strategy instruction for solving word meanings in one or two strategies (e.g., using context, word parts) impacts generalized comprehension. However, there is some indication that teaching students to actively monitor their understanding of vocabulary and use flexible strategies to solve word meanings could enhance their comprehension skills.

Wasik, Hindman and Snell's (2016) review found that the effects of interventions featuring book reading are modest and book reading should be considered a beneficial part of a larger system of instruction to build vocabulary, including other activities such as play-based learning opportunities in the infant classes of the primary school. They also highlighted that adult and child interaction during book reading is critical for vocabulary learning to occur.

Hairrell, Rupley and Simmons' (2011) review analysed the effectiveness of the various possible components of vocabulary instruction. They found that contextual analysis instruction increases vocabulary learning and when contextual and morphological analysis were combined in overall analysis, effect size for morphology over the combined effect was $d = 0.59$. The studies

revealed that when semantic strategies were part of a multicomponent vocabulary program, there were positive gains. Semantic instruction was found to be effective with students with limited vocabulary knowledge (Apthorp, 2006) as it created more lasting knowledge. In general, brief, explicit, teacher-led lessons on relevant vocabulary improved student learning and recall of vocabulary. However, there were no studies in this review that compared explicit instruction to non-explicit instruction. Interventions that included multiple exposures had favourable results, though multiple exposures were not studied in isolation. Overall, multiple strategy instruction had positive effects, but as studies used different combinations it is difficult to ascertain the best method. Graphic organisers contributed to positive effects but they were not studied in isolation which makes it difficult to ascertain the particular impact of graphic organizers in learning vocabulary.

Lawson-Adams and Dickinson's (2020) review of lexical representations found gestures, pictures, and sounds can help support word learning as it provides students with multimodal access to vocabulary learning (Rowe et al., 2013; Tellier, 2008), and is particularly relevant to the learning of academic vocabulary (Townsend, Filippini, Collins, & Biancarosa, 2012). Studies that included songs were particularly effective at encouraging student engagement (Madsen, 1991; Schunk, 1999) and engaging young children in discussions about words enhanced their word knowledge (Beck & McKeown, 2007).

Swanson et al.'s (2011) review found that reading aloud to children had significant, positive effects on children's language, phonological awareness, print concepts, comprehension, and vocabulary outcomes were found from interventions that used dialogic reading; repeated reading of stories; story reading with limited questioning before, during, and/or after reading; computer-assisted story reading; and story reading with extended vocabulary activities.

Reynolds, Wheldall and Madelaine (2011) included *The National Reading Panel* (NICHD, 2000) findings in their review, which indicated that vocabulary can be enhanced through storybook reading, listening activities and computer-assisted instruction. Other useful strategies include introducing words before reading them in text, repeated exposure in different contexts and task restructuring. Vocabulary should be taught both incidentally and directly using multiple methods. This point was also echoed in Hattie's (2009) synthesis of meta-analyses.

Foorman et al.'s (2016) review highlighted the importance of teaching academic language skills, including the use of inferential and narrative language, and vocabulary knowledge to

children. Instruction on reading skills should be combined with instruction on academic language skills so that students will understand the meaning of the words, sentences, and text they read.

Grover (2017) highlighted the importance of explicitly teaching word meaning, and the need for review and multiple exposures to target vocabulary (Nielsen & Friesen, 2012). Her research found that extended discussion resulted in greater word learning than either incidental exposure or embedded instruction (Coyne et al., 2009). In addition, semantic instruction or anchored instruction (paying attention to spoken or written forms of the word) was more effective than restricting word instruction to defining words in kindergarten. Teachers' use of extra-textual talk during shared reading in preschool improved children's vocabulary knowledge (Zucker et al., 2013). Dickinson and Porche (2011) highlighted the importance of exposing young children to challenging, inferential talk (where they discuss topics beyond their immediate context) during book reading as this had a positive effect on vocabulary development.

Sedgwick and Stothard's (2018) review found that studies that focused on shared reading found that both comprehension and vocabulary improved. Their research noted positive effects of 'embedded instruction' when vocabulary was taught in context of a text using child friendly definitions. It also recommends extended vocabulary instruction over an 'embedded instruction' approach which involves a brief discussion. Studies that included phonics, morphological awareness and phonological and orthographic tasks in the follow-up activities, during extended instruction, were more effective in enhancing children's overall vocabulary, when compared to extended instruction alone. However, cumulative review of vocabulary knowledge is essential to ensure long-term word knowledge, with semantic review significantly more effective than embedded review at improving children's word knowledge (Eurydice, 2011).

Cregan (2019) highlighted the importance of the sustained emphasis on the development of vocabulary. Effective vocabulary teaching involves selectively choosing target words to teach, explicitly teaching target vocabulary while also promoting word consciousness which encourages the development of implicit, incidental vocabulary knowledge, providing multiple encounters with target vocabulary, explicitly teaching morphemic analysis to extend word knowledge, use multi-sensory techniques to help anchor word knowledge (Lane & Allen, 2010; Flynt & Brozo, 2008).

Oral Reading Fluency

Hudson, Koh, Moore and Binks-Cantrell's (2020) review of oral reading fluency interventions found large variability in effect sizes across studies. Effect sizes for rate and accuracy measures ranged from negligible to large (i.e., 0.01 to 1.18) and three studies found large effects for prosody outcomes. Effect sizes for reading comprehension ranged between non-significant and large significant effects. Most of the studies focused on speed and rate aspects rather than prosody interventions due to difficulties encountered in measuring this aspect of oral reading fluency. The findings would recommend the use of repeated reading of text to develop the oral reading fluency of students with reading difficulties (see also Reynolds, Wheldall & Madelaine, 2011). However, other studies have reported that repeated readings are more effective if they are guided by a teacher (Rasinski et al., 2009). The review also revealed that one-to-one interventions with a trained model of fluent word reading and accuracy were most effective. Hudson et al. (2020) also found that targeted fluency instruction can promote reading comprehension improvement, as 75% of the studies were found to produce small to large effects on the oral reading fluency of students with reading difficulties. Additionally, 50% of the studies had small to large effects on reading comprehension outcomes for these students, with the majority of interventions yielding moderate to large effect sizes across a variety of measures. Therefore, oral reading fluency enhancement can be useful in interventions aimed at improving reading comprehension. This recommendation is echoed in Kennedy et al.'s (2012) report. In general, multifaceted interventions that incorporate the teaching of a variety of reading-related skills are more effective than those that target only one skill.

Foorman et al.'s (2016) identified the usefulness of instructional level texts to enable students to practice accurate decoding and encoding, and reread the texts to build oral reading fluency, particularly in intervention settings. The review also recommended that children need to read connected text every day to support reading accuracy, fluency, and comprehension. Indeed, Kennedy et al. (2012) noted the important role of practice in promoting reading fluency. Effective methods to increase reading fluency in young readers and in struggling readers include echo reading, choral reading and reading with a computerised device (Foorman et al, 2016) and also paired repeated reading, assisted reading and phrase reading (Rasinski, Homan & Biggs, 2009; Nichols, Rupley & Rasinski, 2009) which is also recommended in the Eurydice Report (2011). Kennedy et al. (2012) also encourage the use of 'the oral recitation lesson' (ORL), 'fluency

development lessons' (FDLs), 'fluency orientated reading instruction' (FORI), radio reading and Fast Start as approaches that enhance oral reading fluency.

Comprehension

Comprehension is the act of constructing meaning with oral or written text. Comprehension is a complex process involving multiple, reciprocal and interacting factors involving the text (language, genre, purpose), the listener/reader (prior knowledge, skills, strategies, purpose for reading), the activity and the context in which the reading/listening occurs (Duke & Carisle, 2010; Pearson, 2009; RAND Reading Study Group, 2002).

In a seminal meta-analysis of 63 think aloud studies Pressley and Afflerbach (1995) identified the strategies that good readers use in transacting with texts. In an update on this research Afflerbach and Cho (2009) identified these constructively responsive reading strategies as "identifying and remembering important information, monitoring and evaluating" (p.77). The National Reading Panel Report (NRP) (NICHD, 2000) noted a range of effective instructional practices in class including comprehension monitoring, questioning (teacher and child generated), summarising, co-operative learning, text structure knowledge and use of graphic organisers.

Good readers orchestrate a repertoire of strategies as they read and these strategies can be taught in classrooms to increase reading comprehension. For example, the systematic review on questioning as a high level cognitive strategy conducted by Davoudi and Sadeghi (2015) revealed the indispensable role of teacher and student questioning in facilitating critical thinking, writing ability, reading comprehension, subject matter learning, and the development of metacognitive skills. Moreover, Elleman's, (2017) review showed that inference instruction was effective for increasing students' general comprehension, ($d = 0.58$), inferential comprehension, ($d = 0.68$), and literal comprehension, ($d = 0.28$). Clinton et al. (2020) noted the scores on measures for inferential comprehension were higher for narrative texts than expository texts.

Reading comprehension strategies can be introduced and taught individually. However, readers never read with only one strategy in mind. Indeed, it is the flexible selection of a range of comprehension strategies, as part of a self-regulated process, that lies at the heart of good reading. Davis (2013) reviews a number of instructional models, such as Reciprocal Teaching, Collaborative Strategic Reading, CORI, and Transactional Strategies Instruction that involve Multiple Comprehension Strategy Instruction (MCSI). The models reviewed include a number of

common strategies, such as monitoring, making predictions, attending to main ideas, and making connections across texts and experiences.

A note of caution is signalled by Davis (2013), in relation to studies incorporating multiple comprehension strategy instruction which present a proceduralised view of strategic reading, characterised by repeated use of common strategies taught to students in a prescribed sequence. The author espouses the need to help students to become more self-regulated, metacognitive, intentional and reflective as to the identification of reading goals and the selection of strategies to meet those goals.

Explicit Strategy Instruction

Most MCSI models involve explicit or formal instruction of reading comprehension strategies by the teacher which involves demonstrating, modelling, and guiding the reader to use these strategies independently when reading. This involves questioning, prompting, cueing and explaining (Frey & Fisher, 2010 cited in Reynolds, 2017). Reynolds (2017) further notes that successful scaffolding should involve explicit attention to both cognitive and motivational dimensions, where teachers probe and nurture student current knowledge, encourage classroom dialogue and give due attention to creating a collaborative and positive classroom culture.

Text Structure Knowledge

Students construct meaning from text when taught the structure of both narrative and informational (including expository) text structures. Structural awareness improves comprehension because it facilitates a coherent mental representation of text. Awareness of text structures has been associated with better recall of ideas (Ray & Meyer, 2011). The Institute of Education Sciences report, *Improving Reading comprehension in kindergarten through 3rd grade: A practice guide* (Shanahan, Callison, Carriere, Duke, et al., 2010) note moderate evidence to support teaching students to identify and use the text's organisational structure to comprehend, learn, and remember content. Analysis of reviewed literature by Ray and Meyer (2011) suggested that readers of all ages may benefit from explicit instruction in expository text structure knowledge, particularly less-skilled comprehenders. The review by Reynolds (2017) supports this view with a large effect size noted for reading comprehension (0.95) when students were intentionally scaffolded to develop text structure knowledge. Teachers should choose texts that support text structure knowledge and support their learning goals (Shanahan et al., 2010).

Integrated Literacy Instruction: Effects on Comprehension and Vocabulary

Students with limited vocabulary knowledge can encounter difficulties with reading comprehension because vocabulary is an essential enabler of reading comprehension development (Wright & Cervetti, 2017). Hwang et al., (2021) investigated whether integrated literacy and content area instruction (i.e. science and social studies) would enhance vocabulary and comprehension. Conclusions from this meta-analysis of (quasi)experimental studies revealed significant effect sizes (ES) for both vocabulary (ES=0.91) and comprehension (ES=0.40) and content area knowledge (ES=0.89). This suggests that integrated literacy and content area instruction has the potential to enhance both vocabulary and comprehension while concurrently developing content area knowledge throughout the primary school system.

Effective Writing Instruction in Primary School

Writing is a complex problem-solving process (McCutchen, Teske, & Bankston, 2008) and depends, at least in part, on the writer's understanding of and experience with the writing process and with the various skills involved in composing a text. The capacity to write well is fundamental to success in school and supports future learning of more complex knowledge, which in turn supports individuals in discovering and reaching their potential in life (Graham, 2019; Kennedy & Shiel, 2019). In line with UNESCO (2021), Camacho, Alves & Boscolo (2021, p.214) consider writing to be 'a key skill in the twenty-first century and a gateway to lifelong learning, employment, and social inclusion'. Writing also provides the means for 'personal reflection, thought, creativity, creation of meaning and exchange of ideas, as well as a complement to other modes of communication in a world of multimodal texts' (Patino, Calixto, Chiappe, & Almenarez, 2020, p. 494). Writing development is influenced by the 'affordances of classrooms which can either constrain and hinder it or propel it forward' (Kennedy & Shiel, 2022, p.1). The current review examines meta analyses and systematic reviews to identify effective pedagogies to support the writing development of primary children (K-6th grade) in relation to writing processes, knowledge for writing, development of foundational writing skills, the role of engagement in writing development and reading writing connections. First, studies of writing interventions and writing process-based approaches are explored. Second, studies primarily focused on grammar, spelling and morphology are synthesised. Third, studies examining the role played by handwriting and keyboarding skills in supporting transcription and text generation are investigated. The fourth

section presents findings highlight the impact of interventions which combine reading and writing. Finally, studies exploring the key role of motivation, engagement and writer identity are presented.

Studies of Writing Pedagogies and Approaches

Overview of the Studies

Five of the reviews explored the impact of a range of interventions on writing in K-12th grade classrooms. The sixth review, Graham (2019), was not a systematic review per se; rather the aim was to identify factors that hinder writing development. It drew on 28 studies involving a mix of survey, observation, and mixed method studies involving the writing practices of more than 7,000 teachers. Two thirds of the studies included were located in the US with the remainder in Europe, China, New Zealand and South America.

Three of the systematic reviews explored the impact of process-based models of writing instruction (Graham & Sandmel, 2011; Graham et al., 2012; Slavin et al., 2019). Graham & Sandmel (2011) included 29 studies of such models in Grades 1-12 while Graham et al.'s (2012a, 2012b) review focused on elementary writing interventions (K-6th grade). It drew on 115 studies, of which 30 focused on Grades 1-3 with the remainder examining grades 4-6. Interventions were only included if they had been tested in at least four different studies.

Slavin et al. (2019) took a slightly broader approach. The 14 studies in their review (grades 2-12) investigated the impact of particular programmes and approaches on children's writing and categorised them into three main groups:

1. Writing process models: 4 studies utilising either Self-Regulated Strategy Development (SRSD) or the 6+1 Trait Writing Model
2. Cooperative learning: 4 studies utilising Writing Wings, Student Team Writing, Collaborative Strategic Reading (CSR) or Expert 21.
3. Programs integrating reading and writing: 6 studies using the College-Ready Writers Program (CRWP), Pathway or Philosophy for Children (P4C), Academic language instruction for all students (ALIAS) or Expository Reading and Writing Course (ERWC).

All of the process-based studies, one each of the cooperative learning and integrated reading and writing studies were conducted with children in primary school (grades 3-6; aged 7-13) while the remainder were with children in middle school (grades 6-8) and high school (grades 8-12). Two of the five reviews explored studies in relation to particular age ranges. McMaster et al., (2018), a best evidence synthesis, explored writing in the early years only (K-3rd grade) while

(Koster et al., 2015) focused on interventions in upper primary only (Grades 4-6). There is considerable overlap between these studies and those of Graham et al., 2012).

McMaster et al. (2018) drew on earlier meta analyses (Graham et al., 2012a, 2012b) and was particularly focused on interventions for children identified as having a learning difficulty. It drew on studies which aligned with theoretical models of writing development (e.g. Berninger & Swanson, 1994; Hayes & Flower, 1980 cited in McMaster et al., 2018). Cognitive models of writing highlight the role of cognitive resources such as memory (working, short and long-term memory) and self-regulation, text transcription and text generation and key processes such as planning, translating and evaluating and revising on writing development and writing quality. Twenty-eight studies met the inclusion criteria which included interventions related to transcription (i.e. transcribing letters, words, sentences, or longer units of discourse into print (typing/handwriting/spelling), text generation (i.e. translating ideas into words, sentence longer discourse units (word, word selection and sentence/story construction), and/or self-regulation (i.e., strategies designed to facilitate writers' use of planning, reviewing, revising).

Koster et al. (2015) responded to research in the Netherlands which identified that the majority of students leaving primary school had not developed writing to the level required for success at post-primary school (Henkens, 2010) and that there was slower growth in children's writing between grades 4-6 (Kühlemeier et al., 2013). Similar to earlier meta-analyses cited (e.g. Graham & Perin 2007; Hillocks, 1984) they grouped the 32 interventions into 10 categories according to the main reported focus of a given study (strategy instruction, text structure instruction, peer assistance, process approach, feedback, grammar instruction, prewriting activities, 'goal setting', evaluation and revision) while recognising that categories overlapped and were not mutually exclusive (e.g. prewriting activities and revision are elements of the process approach and of strategy instruction). Key findings from across these five reviews are presented in the following subsections.

Process-based Approaches to Writing

There is considerable variation in the literature on the precise characteristics of process-based approaches to writing popularised by seminal writing workshop studies in the 1980s (e.g. Graves, 1983, Calkins, 1983) and 'no universally agreed on definition' (Graham & Sandmel, 2011, p.396). However, key principles include opportunities for students to write for real purposes and audiences

and ownership over writing through choice of topic and determination of time spent on the topic. Additionally, children engage in iterative cycles of writing involving the three main writing processes: planning (generating and organising ideas); translating (capturing ideas in written form); and reviewing (evaluating, editing, revising). Instructional frameworks for process-based approaches include daily time to write which incorporates mini-lessons, conferencing and a social dimension in the form of a share session.

In general, for mainstream classes, process writing instruction results in a statistically significant but relatively modest improvement in the overall quality of writing. In the Graham & Sandmel study (2011) the mean average weighted ES computed with a random-effects model was 0.34 while in Graham et al. (2012) it was 0.40. Smaller but statistically significant effect sizes (0.17) were reported by Slavin et al., (2019). In contrast, Koster et al. (2015) reported negative effects for process writing. However, they noted that only three process-based studies were included in their review and that such a small sample lacked the statistical power required to detect real differences. A further complication was the fact that two of the studies cited compared variations of process-based approaches (Arter et al., 1994; DeJarnette (2008): process approach vs. 6+1 Traits model. They also hypothesised that process-based approaches may be challenging for young writers as they address many skills at once and young writers are still acquiring foundational writing skills.

Process-based studies are further compromised by the considerable variation in the implementation of writing workshops which in turn mediate the impact on children's writing quality and writing engagement. Mediating factors (Troia, 2009) include the degree of attention and specificity given to goal setting and feedback; classroom environment and interactions (encouraging versus more punitive); and the level of collaboration and agentic behaviour promoted (many versus few opportunities). Twenty-five studies in the Graham et al. (2012) meta-analysis provided strong evidence for teaching students to consider the purpose of writing and the intended audience for the text. Additionally, limitations in study designs or reporting of dimensions of studies (such as duration, genre(s), number of assignments students worked on, nature of pre-and post-test, control conditions) mean that findings must be interpreted with caution (Koster et al., 2015; Slavin et al., 2019).

The Role of Strategy Instruction in Writing Process Pedagogy

Graham et al. (2012a) define a strategy as a '*series of actions (mental, physical or both) that writers undertake to achieve their goals. Strategies are tools that can help students generate content and carry out components of the writing process,*' (p.15). Twenty-five of the studies in the review provided robust evidence for explicit instruction in a variety of strategies for each component of the writing process: how to plan, draft, revise, edit and publish writing (effect sizes for: strategy instruction: +1.02; prewriting activities: +.54). Similar findings were found by McMaster et al. (2018) and Koster et al. (2015). However, in general, insufficient attention is given to teaching these writing processes (Graham, 2019).

A particular form of strategy instruction, Self-Regulated Strategy Development (SRSD, Graham & Harris, 1996) has been tested in a wide range of interventions (see Kennedy & Shiel, 2019), with a wide variety of class levels and some with typically achieving and many with struggling writers (e.g. Tracy, Reid & Graham, 2009; Glaser & Brunstein, 2007; Harris, Graham & Mason, 2006; Garcia-Sanchez & Fidalgo Redondo, 2006 cited in Graham et al., 2012a). SRSD draws on mnemonic strategies to help writers remember steps in a particular strategy (e.g. POW (Pick an Idea; Organise my notes; Write and say more; TREE, persuasive writing strategy (Topic sentence; Reasons (3+); Explain reasons; Ending (wrap it up right). McMaster et al. (2018) examining 15 studies of SRSD (K-3rd grade studies of children with learning difficulties) which they deemed to be high-quality, found that pairing POW-a general planning strategy – with TREE-a genre-specific strategy – is a useful approach to improve young children's fictional and persuasive writing. They suggest that SRSD in these studies was successful as it emphasised critical writing strategies that are of particular focus in the early grades (e.g., planning, organizing, adding details), and that the strategy structure supports students' independent use of these strategies which can be applied across multiple genres.

Questions have been raised about the quality of some SRSD studies (Slavin, et al., 2019). They note that most SRSD evaluations have taken place in special education settings and as such are aimed at helping 'poor readers/ poor writers' and so may not be warranted for the general population. Additionally, some studies did not meet sample size, duration or control group requirements for their review. They further highlight contrasting results between two larger scale studies of adapted SRSD in the UK. Torgerson & Torgerson (2014) focused on low-achievers reported a positive effect size of +0.74. A larger one-year (grade 5) and two-year trial (grades 4 &

5) (Torgerson et al., 2018) involving low, middle and high-achieving children reported a non-significant effect of +0.11. The weighted mean for all students across both studies was +0.22 ($p = .06$). An interesting finding in the 2018 study was that measures of non-writing outcomes also explored in the study, benefitted the control group rather than the experimental group (reading (ES= -0.23, $p < .05$), spelling (ES= -0.22, $p < .10$), and math (ES= -0.22, $p < .10$) for the one-year trial, and for reading (ES= -0.17, $p < .05$), spelling (ES= -0.28, $p < .05$), and math (ES= -0.30, $p < .05$) in the two-year trial) leading Slavin et al. (2019) to conclude that such negative findings may have arisen due to an excessive focus on writing which left insufficient time for developing reading, spelling and math skills. This underscores the need for careful balance of time and focus in studies so that unintended and undesired consequences do not arise. Further research aimed at developing and evaluating interventions focusing on text generation for young students is required (McMaster et al., 2018).

Graham et al. (2012b) in a second study investigating effective instructional practices for teaching writing to elementary grade students calculated an average weighted ES for 13 writing interventions (tested in at least 4 studies) from 115 documents. Six of the interventions involved explicitly teaching writing processes, skills, or knowledge. All but 1 of these interventions (grammar instruction) produced a statistically significant effect: strategy instruction (ES = 1.02), adding self-regulation to strategy instruction (ES = 0.50), text structure instruction (ES = 0.59), creativity/imagery instruction (ES = 0.70), and teaching transcription skills (ES = 0.55). A further four studies examined the impact of scaffolding or supporting children's writing using prewriting activities (ES = 0.54), peer assistance when writing (ES = 0.89), product goals (ES = 0.76), and assessing writing (0.42). Moderator analyses revealed that the self-regulated strategy development model (ES = 1.17) and a process approach to writing instruction (ES = 0.40) improved how well students wrote.

Importance of Feedback and Self-Regulation for Writing Development

Related to strategy instruction is the suite of studies that combine such instruction with a focus on self-monitoring and self-regulation and feedback mechanisms to the writer. These studies indicate that it is critical that distinct goals are established throughout each of the writing processes and that peer and teacher feedback should be specific to both processes and writing product if writing quality is to improve. This is particularly important for struggling writers who find it difficult to

self-monitor or evaluate particular strengths and weaknesses in their writing and who need multiple demonstrations and opportunities to transfer skills and strategies to their independent writing (Kennedy & Shiel, 2019). Graham, Harris and Hebert (2011) reported an effect size 0.71 derived from six studies in relation to peer review while Graham et al. (2012) reported large effect sizes for peer assistance when writing (+0.89), goal-setting (+0.76) and assessing writing (+0.42). Koster et al.'s (2015) results show even larger effects and indicate that the most effective interventions to improve students' writing are, in order of effect sizes: goal setting (+2.03), strategy instruction (+0.96), text structure instruction (+0.76), feedback (+0.59), and peer assistance (+0.88). Graham, Hebert and Harris's (2015) meta-analysis on the role played by formative assessment in enhancing writing quality illustrates the magnitude of the effects of timely feedback on the quality of students' writing in Grades 1-8, which was strong regardless of whether the feedback was given by adults (effect size = 0.87), peers (0.58), self (0.62) or computers (0.38). Success is, however, contingent on modelling these feedback processes for students and engaging them in using relevant evaluation criteria (Kennedy & Shiel, 2019). Similarly, Slavin et al. (2019) argue that to be effective, programmes should teach students to assess their own and others' drafts, to give feedback and provide insight into effective writing strategies.

Linked to feedback and self-regulation are studies which employ co-operative learning and collaborative writing opportunities. Though similar to writing process models which use a plan-draft-revise-edit cycle, they place a far greater emphasis on small group cooperative writing where children students support each other with writing. Slavin et al. (2019) investigated four such programmes (Writing Wings, Student Team Writing, Collaborative Strategic Reading (CSR), Expert 21) and reported overall weighted mean effect sizes (+0.16) similar to process based approaches (+0.17) and studies integrating reading and writing approaches (=0.19).

Studies on the Conventions of Writing

Research at primary level highlights an over-emphasis on grammar, handwriting and spelling and insufficient attention to the writing processes (e.g. planning, reviewing) reviewed earlier (Graham, 2019). This is borne out across studies and nations (e.g. Cutler & Graham, 2008; Dockrell et al., 2016; Rietdijk et al., 2018, cited in Graham, 2019) leading Daffern, McKenzie & Hemmings (2017, cited in Kennedy & Shiel, 2019) to argue that *'one of the key challenges is to ensure instruction in spelling, grammar and punctuation are carefully balanced with other important*

aspects of written text creation, such as text structure, vocabulary usage and handwriting' (p.84). Nevertheless, these skills play a key role in writing development and given that children who struggle with these skills will have less cognitive resources available to devote to the higher-order dimensions and processes of writing (Berninger et al., 1992 cited in McaMaster et al., 2018), it is essential that they are taught explicitly in developmentally appropriate ways. In the following subsections, findings from systematic reviews and meta-analyses are presented on the role and impact of grammar instruction on writing quality and followed by transcription skills (spelling and morphology, handwriting and keyboarding).

Role of Grammar in Writing Pedagogy and Impact on Writing Quality

There are conflicting findings on the role of grammar in writing pedagogy and its potential to impact on writing quality. Myhill & Watson's (2014) review of the literature explored the question: Does explicit knowledge of grammar support writing development and attainment in writing? They argue that the '*history of grammar teaching over the past 50 years is one of contestation, debate and dissent and 50 years on we are no closer to reaching a consensus about the role of grammar in the English/Language Arts curriculum'* (p.41). Historical and theoretical perspectives are considered and studies examined dated from the 1960s to the present day and were situated across the education continuum from primary school to high school and one university level study. The review highlighted how the place of grammar in the curriculum has undergone several pendulum swings from abandonment of formal grammar teaching in curricula in the 60s and 70s, to an understanding of its contribution to literacy development more generally through the work on Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) (e.g. Halliday, 1985; 2003). Derewianka & Jones (2010) cited in Myhill & Watson (2014, p.45) highlight:

Whereas traditional approaches conceive of grammar as a set of structures which can be assessed as correct or incorrect, Halliday sees language as a resource, a meaning-making system through which we interactively shape and interpret our world and ourselves. (p.9)

SFL research is extended by contemporary scholars who view grammar as part of a social semiotic system (e.g. Schleppegrell's body of work: 2007, 2012 cited in Myhill, 2014) and those who view it as a 'design tool' (Myhill, 2011, cited in Kennedy & Shiel, 2022) with potential to impact of writing quality.

Grammar has been reinstated in national curricula frameworks more recently (DfE, 2013; ACARA, 2009; Common Core State Standards, 2012 cited in Myhill & Watson, 2014). Its

potential to impact writing quality depends on how it is conceptualised and presented in curricula, the extent to which it is taught in isolation and ‘as an arbiter of accuracy’ (Myhill & Watson, 2014, p.45) or within the context of authentic writing where it can be utilised as a design tool for communicating. Previous early meta-analyses (cited in Graham et al., 2012a) concluded that grammar teaching in isolation has little or no effect on students’ writing (Hillocks and Smith, 1991) or a negative effect on it (Braddock et al., 1963). More recently, Graham & Perin (2007, cited in Graham 2012a) and Koster et al. (2015) also found negative effects of systematic teaching of the parts of speech and structure of sentences on writing quality. In contrast, Slavin et al. (2019) highlighted its value if it was taught in the context of children’s writing while several studies reviewed in Myhill & Watson’s (2014) review (e.g. Jones et al. 2013; Fearn & Farnan, 2007; Myhill et al., 2012) point to the value of conceptualising grammar more broadly. These studies emphasise a focus on the lexical, syntactical and rhetorical features of language within the context of writing instruction and explicit teaching to demonstrate how such knowledge can transform writing quality. The Myhill et al. (2012) study was a large randomised control trial which while it achieved an overall significant positive effect, it was stronger for the more-able students and mediated by teachers’ level of linguistic subject knowledge and level of comfort teaching such linguistic content in the context of writing. Such findings, again underscore, the complexity of writing and the level of PCK required by teachers to teach literacy well. Many studies have examined sentence-combining (another aspect of grammar teaching) as a strategy given that it has been repeatedly identified as important in teaching students to construct more complex and sophisticated sentences; however, these studies have been critiqued, as very few examine whether the overall quality of written composition is improved. Students may improve their ability to combine sentences but this may not transfer into more sophisticated writing.

In another related strand of research, Jagaiah et al. (2020) conducted a meta-analysis of Syntactic Complexity Measures (SCMs) studies and how syntax varies by genre, grade-level, students’ writing abilities, and writing quality. They synthesised 36 studies across Kindergarten to 12th grades spanning 1970 to 2019. They note that syntactical complexity is an abstract concept with no one agreed definition in the literature. It is measured in various ways such as T-units (thought units), clauses and clause length and phrases within sentences. The variation in T-unit definitions across studies has made it difficult to directly compare results. Longer T-units were more evident in the argumentative genre. A further finding was that as students mature, they tend

to construct more complex sentences. In general, syntactically complex sentences were observed at higher grade levels and in texts written by higher-achieving students. Furthermore, competence in constructing longer and more syntactically complex sentences did not necessarily translate to students' ability to generate ideas and communicate more effectively in connected writing, though it may support less proficient writers in freeing up the mental resources required for idea generation and higher order dimensions of writing. Jagaiah et al. conclude further research is required if SCM research is to inform recommendations for classroom practice. Further research should group a number of SCMs within studies, explore their impact across a range of genre, include larger sample sizes and greater attention to inter-rater reliability.

Impact of Spelling Instruction on Writing

The capacity to write well with accurate grammar, spelling and punctuation 'remains a fundamental part of being a literate writer' (Patino, Calixto, Chiappe, & Almenarez, 2020, p. 494). Difficulties with spelling can negatively influence writing quality as it may affect a student's motivation, sense of self-efficacy and confidence to write (Snowling, 2000, cited in Kennedy et al., 2012) and may limit word choice as students are less likely to choose ambitious words they can't spell (Graham et al., 2012a, 2012b). Spelling is an integral part of the orthographic knowledge that underlies efficient, automatic generation of words during writing, and efficient, automatic perception of words during reading (Kennedy et al., 2012). Snow, Griffin, and Burns (2005, cited in Kennedy et al., 2012) note, '*spelling and reading build and rely on the same mental representation of a word. Knowing the spelling of a word makes the representation of it sturdy and accessible for fluent reading*' (p. 86).

Graham and Santangelo's (2014) meta-analysis investigated eight research questions exploring the extent to which spelling instruction made children in K-12th grade better spellers, readers and writers (Table 1). The review included 53 studies grouped into three categories:

1. formal spelling instruction versus no instruction/unrelated instruction
2. more formal spelling instruction versus less formal spelling instruction
3. formal spelling instruction versus spelling is caught approaches.

Likewise, Kent & Wanzek, (2016) examined the relationship between component skills (handwriting and spelling) and writing quality and production across PreK to 12th grade in 38 studies published between 1988-2013. They explored three research questions:

1. What is the relationship between handwriting, spelling, reading, and oral language and writing quality and writing production across Grades K to 12?
2. Does grade level of students moderate the relationship between component skill or process and writing outcomes?
3. Do these relationships differ for students with academic difficulties (e.g., high-incidence disabilities and/or struggling readers or writers)?

Results across both meta-analyses provided strong and consistent support for the formal teaching of spelling and results were generally consistent, regardless of students' grade level or literacy skills. Kent et al. (2016) analysis confirmed moderate, significant correlations between each individual component skills and students' writing quality but generally weak relationships with the amount of writing produced. Student grade level and student ability level did not appear to moderate the relationship between these factors and writing quality. The mean ES of the correlation between spelling ability and the amount of writing students was small but statistically significant. Additionally, like Graham & Santangelo (2014; see Table 1, a positive moderate relationship was found between reading achievement and the quality of student's written composition ($r=.47$). The relationship between reading achievement and writing production was strongest for students in primary grades. Ouellette and Sénéchal (2017 cited in Kennedy & Shiel, 2019, 2022) argue that children who are encouraged to use invented spelling in their written work attain higher reading scores than children who learn to spell in the traditional, conventional manner.

Overall, Graham & Santangelo (2014) consistently found that formal spelling instruction improved students' spelling performance providing strong support for directly and systematically teaching students how to spell. It further recommended that teachers in primary grades should continue to explicitly and systematically teach spelling while teachers in the upper elementary grades should place more emphasis on such instruction and schools should consider if such instruction should be extended into middle school. Additionally, future analyses of the spelling instruction literature should examine if specific kinds of spelling interventions produce different results.

Table 1: Summary of results (Graham & Santangelo, 2014).

Research Questions	Results (Average weighted effect sizes)
1. Does formal instruction produce greater spelling gains than no spelling instruction?	Formal spelling instruction superior to no or unrelated instruction (ES 0.54); Positive across all studies.
2. Does more formal spelling instruction time produce greater spelling gains?	Increasing the amount of spelling instruction had a positive impact on performance (ES 0.70)
3. Does formal instruction produce greater spelling gains than spelling is caught approaches?	Formal spelling instruction superior to ‘spelling is caught’ approaches for learning to spell (ES 0.43); 87 % produced overall positive effect.
4. Does formal instruction produce gains in students’ correct spelling in writing?	Formal spelling instruction resulted in more correct spelling when writing (ES 0.94). All but one study had an overall positive effect
5. Does formal instruction produce spelling gains that are maintained over time?	Gains from explicit spelling instruction were maintained over time (ES 0.53); All studies yielded positive effects
6. Does formal spelling instruction enhance phonological awareness?	Formal spelling instruction enhanced students’ phonological awareness skills (ES 0.51); All but one study produced a positive effect.
7. Does formal spelling instruction enhance reading?	Formal spelling instruction enhanced students’ reading performance (ES 0.44); All but one study produced an overall positive effect.
8. Does formal spelling instruction enhance writing quality?	Formal spelling instruction did not statistically enhance students’ writing performance (ES 0.19) across six studies.

There is debate in the field as to whether spelling skills learned through formal instruction actually generalise to writing composition. Graham (1999, cited in Graham & Santangelo, 2014) reported that teachers sometimes express the view that formal spelling instruction does not generalise to students’ writing. The current study finds small non-significant effects for spelling instruction on writing quality, though Graham & Santangelo (2014) highlight that this result may be because writing and writing instruction in the six studies occurred infrequently or not at all. In relation to writing development of young children, the development of proficient transcription skills may free up cognitive resources for higher-level processes required for writing tasks (Kent et al., 2016). This correlates with other research which highlights that young children’s imagination, creativity and thinking capacities outstrip their transcription skills initially, and that providing invented spelling opportunities within authentic writing contexts supports their agency in writing and assists them in capturing their thoughts in writing. Invented spelling has also been shown to play a causal role in literacy development more generally (Ouellette & Sénéchal, 2017; Read, 1971; Clarke, 1988 cited in Kennedy & Shiel, 2022). Relative to all component skills examined by Kent & Wanzel (2016), the quality of writing was most strongly correlated with

transcription skills, that is, handwriting fluency and spelling, as well as with reading achievement. Poor spelling constrains writers' cognitive resources as well as impacting negatively on assessment results due to poor presentation.

Handwriting and Quality of Writing

Handwriting is a central component in cognitive models of writing (e.g. Berninger & Swanson, 1994; Berninger and Amtmann, 2003 cited in Kennedy & Shiel, 2019) which facilitates the translation of ideas into written form. Automaticity in handwriting is considered to be a key skill contributing to skilled writing composition, though it is often 'considered by many researchers and educators as solely a motor and mechanical act, its role in writing is easily belittled' (Limpo & Graham, 2020, p.312). Children who experience handwriting difficulties can develop low self-efficacy and a mindset that they cannot write which can lead to them avoiding or resisting writing (Santangelo & Graham, 2016; Feng et al., 2019). While the six reviews examined here report positive results for handwriting instruction, researchers acknowledge that there is a need for more and better designed studies examining the impact of handwriting instruction on writing with a wider range of students.

Limpo and Graham (2020) situate their review of handwriting within the context of a writers in community model (Graham, 2018 cited in Limpo & Graham 2020) which combines cognitive and social dimensions of writing. In this model, writing (and by extension handwriting) is viewed as a social act which is 'simultaneously shaped and constrained by context, the capabilities and perceptions of writers and collaborators operating in said context' (p.313). Their review encompassed evidenced-based practices for writing at the letter (e.g., alphabet exercises), word/sentence (e.g., copying exercises), and text (e.g., authentic writing tasks). They note that difficulties with handwriting interferes with writers' ideas and text generation, places burdens on working memory, affects sense of self-efficacy and can create difficulties for the reader if the product is illegible or challenging to read. For emergent writers or children with handwriting or spelling difficulties transcription can be a bottleneck (Hayes & Olinghouse, 2015, cited in Graham, 2019; Feng et al., 2019) as having to concentrate so much attention on forming letters means less attention can be devoted to monitoring and appraising what has been written. Slow writers may lose ideas as their handwriting cannot not keep up with their idea generation. It is therefore critical that young writers develop fluent and automatic handwriting, keyboarding, and spelling skills to

make transcription more automatic. Though digital devices are now more prevalent in schools, handwriting remains a key skill in early years' classrooms and is the main format of written texts within primary schools.

Evidenced-based practices for handwriting instruction

Handwriting is a '*complex neuromotor skill that encompasses numerous cognitive and motor processes operating in concert...handwriting relies on the close articulation between orthographic and motor skills*' (Limpo & Graham, 2020, p.316). Handwriting can be assessed for accuracy, speed and legibility. A valid and reliable instrument for measuring legibility is the Test of Legible Handwriting (Larsen & Hammil, 1989, cited in Limpo & Graham, 2020). Educators are encouraged to obtain three handwriting tasks (one copying task and two free writing tasks) and to compare the samples to a set of graded samples and to score them on a scale from 1 to 9. Accuracy and speed can be assessed through timed alphabet and copying tasks (Berninger et al., 1992; Kimet al., 2011, cited in Limpo & Graham, 2020) e.g. writers are asked to write the lower case alphabet, as often as possible in 15, 30 or 60 seconds and scored according to alphabetical order, correct formation and legibility. Similarly, in copy tasks writers are asked to copy a sentence (s) as often as possible within 90 seconds which is scored according to number of words correctly copied. Studies on accuracy and speed highlight differences between primary and post-primary student and undergraduate college students speed and accuracy which demonstrate that fluent and accurate handwriting takes time to develop though its instruction is often confined to primary years only (Limpo & Alves, 2013; Connelly, 2007; Graham, 1998). Girls typically out-perform boys on handwriting (e.g. Berninger & Fuller, 1992; Cordeiro et al. 2018 cited in Limpo & Graham, 2020).

There is a dearth of research on how handwriting is actually taught in education settings (Limpo & Graham, 2020; Santangelo & Graham, 2016). Fancher et al. (2018) investigating handwriting acquisition and interventions in Preschool to 2nd grade (15 studies reviewed) reported that with the influence of technology in classrooms that time for handwriting had declined. This trend is a cause for concern given the theorised link between handwriting and 'proximal and potentially distal educational outcomes including reading and literacy' (Graham et al., 2008 cited in Fancher et al., 2018, p.455). Drawing on fMRI technologies, there is increasing evidence from developmental psychology field with pre-school children that 'writing letters mediates neural specialization' (James & Engelhardt, 2012; Li & James, 2016, cited in Fancher et al. 2019). This

body of work has identified ‘discrete patterns of neural activation associated with common forms of early writing instruction (i.e., tracing, typing, and forming letters)’ which has provided new insights into instructional and environment conditions linking handwriting and letter recognition in pre-school children. Fancher et al. (2018 citing Pelatti, Piasta, Justice, and O’Connell, 2014) also report that though writing can comprise up to 42% of a student’s day in elementary school, formal handwriting instruction is inconsistent ranging from no direct instruction to reliance on a manualized handwriting programs while in Pre-K children spend as little as one minute daily on handwriting.

Likewise, Limpo & Graham (2020) found large variations in teaching time (from 2-60 minutes daily) amongst elementary teachers. During kindergarten and Grades 1–3, handwriting development is best facilitated by distributed practice, up to a total of 50 to 100 minutes a week as students learn to name and form each letter. Five hours of handwriting training has been found to be effective in increasing the cursive writing legibility of children in grade 5 who had slower writing fluency than their peers. Studies cited in Limpo & Graham, (Alves et al., 2016; Berninger et al., 1997; Graham et al., 2000; Jones and Christensen, 1999; Limpo and Alves, 2018) indicate that effective handwriting programmes vary in total duration (6.6 hrs. to 20 hrs.) and vary in lesson length and distribution (biweekly to daily lessons of 10 to 30 minutes). Santangelo and Graham (2016) found that students in receipt of 10 hours made greater legibility gains than those who received eight hours or less and students from grades 5 and up made better fluency gains than children in grades 4 and below. They note that a certain level of competence is required before fluency gains can be maximised. Additionally, compared to students who received little or no instruction in handwriting, handwriting instruction produced statistically significant gains in the quality (ES=0.84), length (ES= 1.33), and fluency of students’ writing (ES=0.48). Similar findings were reported by Feng et al., (2019).

Critically, in the early years, handwriting instruction should target the name and form of each letter (Limpo & Graham, 2020). Effective teaching requires visuals of each letter (with cues as to the nature, order and direction of the letter strokes), teacher modelling of the letter formation, opportunities for children to write the letter from memory. The key is to enable children to connect names and forms of letters in memory and to provide activities that require them to produce the letters quickly in alphabet writing activities before moving to words and sentences. Timed activities promote fluency while untimed activities encourage children to focus on form.

Fancher et al. (2018) found tasks that required ‘self-generated letter writing or approximation of letters or symbols resulted in neural activation of networks associated with known reading and visual perception networks’ (p.458) and that writing letters is more effective than just seeing or saying letters. This finding is linked to the earlier discussion on the key role of invented spelling in writing.

Four studies (Limpo & Graham, 2020) involving 478 students in kindergarten through fourth grade, examined the impact of teaching handwriting using a multisensory approach. Positive results were only reported in one of the studies and effect size (0.02) was not significant. Opportunities to write daily in authentic contexts not only promotes handwriting fluency but provides children with a purpose for writing and enhances motivation to write and strengthens early reading development.

Santangelo & Graham’s meta-analysis (2016) examined 80 studies across K-12. They found that handwriting practice is beneficial for Kindergarten through 9th grade and that older students struggling with handwriting can benefit from age-appropriate handwriting instruction. Effect sizes in their study demonstrated significant and consistent effects of handwriting instruction on handwriting fluency (ES = 0.63) as well as on the amount (ES = 1.33), quality (ES = 0.84), and fluency (ES = 0.48) of students’ writing. Current research (Limpo & Graham, 2020; Santangelo & Graham, 2016; Fancher et al., 2018) reveals no empirical evidence for the teaching of motor skills (ES=0.10 for legibility and -0.07 for fluency) or other types of sensory motor skills without explicit handwriting practice if the goal is to improve handwriting. Schwellnus, Cameron & Carnahan (2012), however, cite two studies (Zwicker & Hadwin, 2009; Hoy, Egan, & Feder, 2011) which found that considerable practice is needed and that cognitive approaches worked best for children beyond Grade 1 and sensorimotor practice was more effective with younger children. However, Fancher et al., (2018, Pre-K to 2nd) reported *‘all forms of self-generated letters were associated with better letter or symbol recognition when compared to other sensori-motor activities such as typing, tracing, passively viewing, and saying the letter name out loud (p.458).* One study of five hours’ duration (Limpo et al., 2018 cited in Limpo & Graham, 2020) brought the handwriting fluency of Portuguese students in 5th grade with slower fluency to the level of their peers. Other benefits were enhanced self-efficacy and text production. The intervention *‘combined explicit instruction with intensive and systematic practice in writing cursive letters, words, and sentences fluently and accurately, through fast-paced activities to write the alphabet and copy*

words or sentences' (Limpo & Graham, 2020, p.322). It is important to note that children in Portugal learn cursive writing in first grade. There is debate in the field on which kind of handwriting form children should be introduced to in primary school.

Schwellnus, Cameron & Carnahan (2012) highlight that up to quarter of North American students (predominantly boys) have handwriting difficulties which impacts negatively on their confidence and self-esteem. They questioned the wisdom of the current practice of teaching both manuscript and cursive writing to students in primary. Their review (69 studies met their inclusion criteria) investigated the origins of the dual instruction and the degree to which research supports teaching both forms. The high level of variation amongst countries, schools and teachers makes it difficult to compare across studies. Historically, manuscript was introduced first as it was thought to be easier to learn and closer to the kinds of letters encountered in reading. Cursive first advocates highlight that children find it easier to make curved lines, that cursive movements are closer to scribbling, faster and involve fewer pen lifts. However, they cite multiple studies (e.g. Otto & Rarick (1969); Duvall (1985), and Karlsdottir (1996) which found no difference in reading ability regardless of which is introduced first. In some European countries and Australia cursive is taught first while in North America manuscript is taught in K-2nd grade and a transition to cursive is generally made in 3rd grade. Explanations for reversals of letters and variation in formation of manuscript letters in children aged 4 to 6 is hypothesised to be due to more immature internal visuomotor representations of hand movements and a wider receptive field (Contreras-Vidal, Bo, Boudreau, & Clark, 2005 cited in Swellnus et al., 2012).

Teaching handwriting via technology resulted in statistically significant improvements (ES= 0.85) in legibility (Santangelo & Graham, 2016). This effect size was based on four studies involving 105 students in grades K-6. Studies varied in their focus e.g. one focused on students with handwriting difficulties, one on students with average handwriting skills, one on average and below average and one representing the full range of HW skills. Though a digitised tablet was used in all four studies, in two of the studies it was used just for copying. Despite advancements in technology (e.g. Rosenblum 2002; Chau et al. 2006 cited in Swellnus et al. 2012), which have enabled objective measurements of children's handwriting performance using a digitizer tablet and a stylus, there is still *'a link between learning letters by hand and the processing of visual letters'* (Schwellnus et al., 2012 p.253: citing James, 2010; Longcamp et al., 2008). Research is not conclusive on which letter format to begin with as there appears to *'be similar but different*

challenges associated with both manuscript and cursive formats, and there does not appear to be strong evidence to support the choice of one over the other or which one is selected in the case where only one format is taught (Schwellnus et al., 2012, p.254).

Graham et al., (2012a) argue that being able to type is a valuable life skill and is increasingly necessary for school (e.g. National Assessments of Educational Progress (NAEP, 2013) in the US requires 4th grade students to complete the writing assessment on the computer). In the Irish context, ePIRLS 2016 data suggested that less than half (47%) of Fourth class pupils agreed a lot that they were good at typing (Eevers & Delaney, 2018). Typing can also be an effective support to students with handwriting difficulties. Graham et al. (2012a) found significant effects on writing quality for word processing (ES= 0.47), extra writing time (ES= 0.30), and comprehensive writing programs (ES= 0.42) resulting in statistically significant impacts on writing quality. A key recommendation was to teach all students to touch type fluently and to compose on the computer. Feng et al., (2019) extended the Kent & Wanzek (2016) study by exploring the associations between handwriting or keyboarding on writing quality across 19 studies involving 3014 students from Kindergarten to adolescence. Accurate, fluent transcription of writer ideas to text relies on the writer's fluency in either handwriting or keyboarding. Both processes rely on visual accurate representations of letters. In keyboarding *'movement patterns and keystrokes must be memorized so that the keyboarder may begin to recognize accurate typing based on kinaesthetic cues, rather than looking at the keyboard to find each letter....while writers executing handwriting must accurately and efficiently form each letter* (Feng et al., p. 37). Findings confirmed previous studies (e.g. Graham et al., 2012a, 2012b; Limpo & Graham, 2020; Kent & Wanzek, (2016) that handwriting fluency is a significant predictor of student performance in relation to writing compositional quality, fluency and substantive quality. Students with better handwriting fluency also had better keyboarding fluency indicating a significant correlation between both operations. When timed students produced more words through keyboarding than handwriting. However, though they spent longer handwriting texts, there was no difference in text length when compared with keyboarding. Overall, there are too few studies comparing keyboarding skills with handwriting skills on compositional writing quality. Feng et al. (2019) report that handwriting contributed as much to writing quality as keyboarding and concluded that students *should 'develop handwriting skills and receive explicit instruction about the technology'* p.56).

Motivational and Affective Dimensions of Writing

Graham (2019) highlights the critical influence of both writers' and teachers' beliefs about writing which can either foster or hinder writing development. Sense of self-efficacy is important for writing development as it determines whether an individual will undertake to write, the degree to which they persist in the face of difficulty and influences effort expenditure, persistence and achievement ((Bruning & Kaufman, 2016; Schunk, 2001, cited in Kennedy & Shiel's 2019). Furthermore, according to Bandura, efficacy judgements 'vary across realms of activity, under different levels of task demands within a given domain, and under different situational circumstances' (p. 42). Self-efficacy can be enhanced by ensuring success for the writer and providing a range of experiences (Pajares, 2007 cited in Kennedy & Shiel 2019, p.12):

- *mastery experience* (the most important criterion for developing self-efficacy in a domain); the impact of mastery experience may be linked to the quality of the information students receive when they perform successfully
- *vicarious experience* (e.g., observing others' performances and assessing one's own capabilities in relation to what is observed); fellow students and teachers can serve as models of writing. Models who demonstrate the ability to cope in the face of difficulties are more effective than models who exhibit complete mastery (Zimmerman & Kitsantas, 2002).
- *social persuasion* (e.g., others expressing beliefs that an individual can perform successfully). Teachers can offer suggestions for improvement and demonstrate their belief that the learner can improve; Bruning and Kauffman note that social persuasion should involve 'long term communication patterns in which teachers show their belief in learners' personal agency' (p. 160), rather than shorter pep-talks.
- *identifying and labelling physiological and emotional states linked to a domain* (e.g., identifying and addressing anxiety about writing in general, or about a particular writing task). Teachers can identify possible challenges to writing and seek to reassure students that they can overcome them.

Early theoretical models of the writing process (e.g. Hayes & Flower, 1980; Berninger & Swanson 1994) and more recently the Writers in Community Model (Graham, 2018 cited in Graham, 2019; Limpo & Graham, 2020), in addition to cognitive dimensions of writing, also highlight the key role of the affective dimensions (attitude, motivation, engagement, self-efficacy, self-regulation, value), which are important at each stage of the writing process (planning, translating, revising). Activities that have been found to build writing motivation include '*pupil choice of topic, connecting to pupils' personal interests, cultures and communities, writing for real purposes and audiences and observing the teacher as a writer*' (Kennedy & Shiel, 2019, p.5). Teachers' beliefs about writing and their dispositions toward writing influence their classroom

practice (Graham & Harris, 2018; Brindle et al, 2016; Troia & Graham, 2016, 2017). Citing research (Woodward, 2013) Graham underscores the importance of relevant stakeholders having a *positive identity as a writer* which it is argued increases the likelihood that they will write, enjoy writing, see the value of writing and teaching it.

Conceptually, efforts to change writing instruction in schools must take into account both the social and the individual aspects of writing (Camacho et al., 2021; Graham, 2019). Children need choice and control over their writing topics and encouraged to write for real purposes and audiences rather than e.g. to fulfil a writing task in school or to perform in a high-stakes test. This involves children writing in a range of informational genres (e.g., access to source material, engaging in critical thinking) as well as engaging in literary and imaginative composition. Research indicates insufficient attention to persuasive and expository informational writing (Parr & Jesson, 2016 cited in Graham, 2019). Graham (2019) also highlights insufficient use of digital tools (e.g. Coker et al., 2016; Simmerman et al., 2012) though most writing outside of school is done digitally (Freedman et al., 2016). Patino et al. (2020) found that ICT facilitates writing development processes, beyond the operational and process perspective (citing Hwang et al., 2014; Pennington et al., 2018; Sulak, 2018). It can enhance writers' agency and self-efficacy and facilitate the organisation of their thought and ideas as they write: 'erasing and correcting without leaving a trace or breaking the paper; and, writing ideas, comments and notes in the same file without messing up what has already been written by the student (Dalton & Hannafin, 1987; Yamaç & Ulusoy, 2016).

Camacho et al. (2021) in a large systematic review of writing motivation in schools between 2000-2018 (82 studies) explored: a) how motivational constructs have been defined in writing research; b) group differences in writing motivation; c) effects of motivation on writing performance; d) evidence of teaching practices to support writing motivation; and e) impact of digital tools on writing motivation. Their review builds on two previous reviews (Ekholm et al. (2018); Klassen 2002). Of the 82 studies, half were conducted in grades 1–5, 14 in grades 6–8, 7 in grades 9–12 (7 studies) and 20 were in multi-grade classes. Almost half of the studies were conducted in the US and the balance across a further 13 countries. The studies primarily employed quantitative methods (n=59) or mixed methods (n=15). There was an overreliance on self-reported or teacher reported scales (n=72) while a small number others drew on student interviews (n = 14), classroom observations (n = 7), document analyses (n = 3), and focus groups (n = 2) to assess

writing motivation. In relation to writing samples, narrative was most often used (22) followed by persuasive (15), informational (11). Digital writing was a feature of 13 studies. Altogether 24 motivation-related constructs were identified, though in almost half of the studies constructs were not clearly defined. Overall, studies (n=22) reported that girls were more motivated to write and in two studies had a stronger writing self-concept than boys though this was countered in an intervention using blogs (Allaire et al., 2013). Mastery goals were most often reported by girls whereas boys were more likely to report performance-approach and performance-avoidance goals (Pajares et al. 2000; Troia, 2013). Overall, a moderate association was found between motivation and performance measures. One of these studies showed that girls with the most negative writing attitudes outperformed boys with the most positive attitudes (Lee, 2013). As has been highlighted above, students' writing motivation was influenced by teaching practices such as handwriting instruction, self-regulated strategy development instruction, opportunities for collaborative writing and use of digital technology (see also digital literacies review: Dwyer et al., 2022). Further longitudinal research is required to extend current understanding in relation to both individual and contextual factors, to test long-term effects of digital tools and to identify evidence-based practices that could inform professional development programs for teachers.

General Conditions for Successful Writing Instruction

In addition to the many aspects of research on writing development in primary grades reviewed above, a number of other dimensions were highlighted as critical to success. These include the provision of adequate time, the motivational and affective dimensions of writing and teachers' professional knowledge and alignment of policies at school and system level.

Time

The first is the provision of adequate time for children to write within an engaged community of writers (Graham et al., 2012a; Graham 2019). Concerns about children's writing development are '*common across the globe...the typical teacher does not devote enough time to writing and writing instruction*' (Graham & Rijlaarsdam, p. 278-281, cited in Graham, 2019). Provision of a daily hour to write from First Grade was one of four key recommendations arising from the 2012a meta-analysis. It was based on the argument that without daily time to write students are unlikely to develop writing to the level required for success in school and in life. How the time is used is

essential as provision of time alone is inadequate. Explicit teaching of relevant and developmentally appropriate skills, strategies and techniques is essential with a recommendation to split the hour (30 min. explicit teaching and 30 min. for children to work on their texts). The 2019 narrative review of 28 survey, observation, and mixed method studies involving more than 7,000 teachers across the US, Europe, China, NZ, and Sth. America revealed daily instructional time is insufficient to impact on the quality of writing e.g. there were infrequent opportunities to engage in different types of writing (e.g., Brindle et al., 2016; Graham, 2014; Kiuahara et al., 2009; Koko, 2016). Linked to time factors was the finding that although teachers reported awareness of effective teaching practices and adaptations, they used them infrequently, about once a month (e.g. Troia & Graham, 2017; Hertzberg & Roe, 2016). Thus, the depth and intensity of instruction required to master the complexities of writing was not accessible to all students.

Teacher professional knowledge and policy

As highlighted in Kennedy & Shiel (2019), teachers require high levels of ‘content knowledge’ (**what** to teach) and ‘pedagogical content knowledge (PCK)’ (**how** best to teach this content) (Shulman, 1987). Enhancing teachers’ PCK ensures that they acquire the particular content, terminology, and body of practices associated with their discipline or subject (Feltovich, Prietula, & Ericsson, 2018, cited in Graham, 2019). Graham (2019) concurs but goes further and argues that enhancing principals’ and policymakers’ knowledge about the writing, how students learn and develop as writers, and effective practices for teaching writing is also critical. Such knowledge and preparation for writing is a key lever for changing classroom writing practices and ensuring the development of a professional vision for writing and the level of commitment required to see it through to enactment (see Kennedy & Shiel 2019 for further detail; for discussion on professional development in literacy more broadly see King et al., 2022; Giblin et al., 2022). Graham (2019) drawing on (Graham et al., 2016; Graham, Harris, et al., 2015; Graham et al., 2015; Graham, et al., 2018; Graham et al., (2018b) concludes the review with 5 key principles which highlight the importance of:

- writing frequently for real and different purposes;
- supporting students as they write
- teaching the needed writing skills, knowledge, and processes;
- creating a supportive and motivating writing environment;
- connecting writing, reading, and learning

Furthermore, successful and systemic success in changing outcomes in relation to effective writing practice requires the alignment of school and national policies. Effective writing instruction is more likely to occur ‘when goals, curriculum, instructional methods, and assessment are aligned’ (Graham, 2019, p. 288). The challenge is to ensure school wide professional conversations that build progression and continuity across the primary school years and to ensure all levels of the system are research-informed with the infrastructure in place to support teachers and children in realising their vision and potential.

Integrating Oral Language, Reading and Writing Instruction

In addition to high levels of reading and writing, oracy is a key factor related to success in school and beyond (Dobinson & Dockrell, 2021). Oracy has been defined as ‘*our ability to communicate effectively using spoken language. It is the ability to speak eloquently, articulate ideas and thoughts, influence through talking, listen to others and have the confidence to express your views*’ (APPG, 2021, p.2). As well as studies investigating one or more of the component skills of reading and writing addressed above, research has tested the effectiveness of combining oral language, reading and writing within interventions. At present, these forms of language are often taught as separate entities which can curtail the levels of progression achievable when they are combined effectively within classrooms according to learners’ needs and stage of development. The following sections explore key findings from this corpus of studies.

Oral Language, Reading and Critical Literacy

The research reviewed here explores the evidence base for the role of oracy in academic achievement at primary level and in literacy in particular. Dobinson & Dockrell’s (2021) systematic review explored the evidence base on universal strategies for the improvement of expressive language skills of 4-11 year olds in the primary classroom. They define universal strategies as strategies that can be used in the regular classroom as part of Tier 1 multilevel systems. Such systems prioritise high-quality classroom literacy instruction to minimise the number of children requiring further Tier 2 or Tier 3 support. Their review draws on studies with oral expressive language as the outcome measured by either standardised tests of oral vocabulary or researcher designed tests or both. A different but related line of research is the investigation of the impact of discussion or dialogic approaches to reading on children’s reading comprehension (EEF, 2021; Murphy et al., 2009). Outcomes are measured by standardised tests of reading achievement

and often involve detailed analysis of literature discussion interactions. Other researchers have examined the evidence base for combining the teaching of reading and writing (Jouhar & Rupley, 2021; Graham, 2020; Graham et al., 2018a; Graham et al., 2018; Graham & Hebert, 2011) with outcome measures examining the impact on both reading and writing quality. The role of oral language is implicit in this latter group of studies, as children use language as a tool to think and talk about their reading materials and their own written compositions (digital and print).

Dobinson & Dockrell (2021) highlight the links between expressive language skills and academic achievement (Roulstone et al., 2011; Spencer et al., 2017), the supportive role these skills play in literacy development in general (Snow, 2016) and in supporting learning across the curriculum (Alexander, 2013; Shiel et al., 2012). Furthermore, quality of oral language has been found to impact on social, emotional, and mental health, both at school (Benner et al., 2002; APPG, 2021) and in later life (Schoon et al., 2010) as it opens access to further education and employment and is key to engaged and agentic citizenship (APPG, 2021; Allington & McGill Franzen, 2021). Dobinson & Dockrell's review draws attention to a gap in the literature as there were no studies that met their inclusion criteria for the 8-11 year age range. They hypothesise (citing Bornstein et al., 2016; Shiel et al., 2012) that the dearth of studies in the upper primary age range may be due to the more subtle growth of language development after age 5, making it more challenging to track. However, they also argue that the stability in language growth may be due to the finding that less attention is paid to oracy and language development in primary classrooms compared with early childhood settings (Law et al., 2019). This correlates with a recent UK government report (APPG, 2021) which highlighted large variations in the time and attention given to oracy within and across schools and the need for 'purposeful and intentional teaching' of oral language (APPG, p.5). It also found that less than half (46%) of primary teachers and a quarter (23%) of secondary teachers reported they felt confident in their understanding of the 'spoken language' requirements outlined in England's National Curriculum.

In Ireland, evidence from the national assessments (NAMER, Kavanagh et al., 2015) reveals that 49% of primary teachers, report they are confident in teaching oral language, 49% report they are somewhat confident and 2% not confident. In highlighting further professional development priorities 25% of teachers indicated oral language. Additionally, in the DEIS context, overall 57% of home school community liaison at primary and post-primary (HSCL) coordinators agreed that poor oral language skills were impacting on pupils' literacy development to a great

extent. When disaggregated, this rose to 79% at primary level where HSCL coordinators reported poor oral language and vocabulary impacted on children’s progress to a great extent. These views were further corroborated by principals who cited students’ poor oral language skills and unemployment in the community as the factors most frequently impacting on pupil achievement.

The 31 studies included in the Dobinson & Dockrell review were primarily implemented in whole class contexts (91%) by classroom teachers (80%) within either single (n=18) or multiple strategy interventions (n =13). The review found significant positive effects (summarised in Table 2) for structured interactive book reading (IBR), structured vocabulary programmes, manualised curricula (involving less qualified staff in US Head Start classrooms) and approaches involving speech and language therapists working in collaboration with teachers. There were positive effects for most single strategy interventions focused on developing vocabulary through IRB. The exception was Ergul et al. (2016) where no effects were found, and which the researcher highlighted was due to poor levels of intervention implementation.

Table 2: Oral language intervention effects on children’s expressive language in primary classrooms (significant effects bolded)

Single Strategy Interventions	
Approach	Average Effect Size (c indicates calculated from data in study)
play-based teaching (n = 3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Baumer et al., 2005: joint adult-child pretence: length: d = 3.32c; linguistic coherence d = 4.4c; narrative complexity d= 0.61c; ● Stagnitti et al., 2016: narrative retell, d = 0.87; ● Hassinger-Das et al., 2016: vocabulary, d = 0.54c
Vocabulary instruction (n = 2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Caron, 2005: no effect ● Benson, 2013: reported significant positive impact on vocabulary (<i>insufficient data to calculate effect size</i>)
Technology effect on vocabulary (n = 3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ihmeideh, 2014: e-books in place of traditional books d = 2.9c; ● Silverman, 2013: single TV view: no effect; ● Silverman, 2013: multiple TV view: <i>d = 0.58</i>
conversation-facilitating approaches on vocabulary (n = 4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ruston & Schwanenflugel, 2010: Conversations between university students and pairs of participants: no effect ● McCabe et al., 2010: university students and individual participants significantly improved narrative competence (<i>insufficient data to calculate effect size</i>) ● Sonmez, 2010: Researcher led whole-class decontextualised conversations: no significant effect
narrative instruction (n = 1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Spencer et al., 2015: narrative retell skills: d = 2.87c, which were sustained through to follow-up at 4 weeks: d = 3.00c
Interactive book reading: (n = 5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Simsek & Erdogan, 2015: small group: d = 1.12c; ● Okyay & Kandir, 2017: whole-class delivery d = 0.62c;

impact on vocabulary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ergül et al., 2016: whole class: not sig $d = 0.8c$; whole class + small group: $d = 0.1c$; • Opel et al., 2009: whole-class $d = 2.00$; • Lever & Sénéchal, 2011: small group IBR: $d = 0.66$.
Multiple Strategy Interventions	
structured IBR + vocabulary instruction ($n = 6$)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coyne et al., 2010, $d = 1.71$; • Gonzalez et al., 2010, $g = 1.01$; • Neuman & Dwyer, 2011, $d = 0.64$; • Neuman & Kaefer, 2018, $d = 0.48$; • Silverman, 2007, $d = 0.58, 0.94$; • Vuattoux et al., 2013: <i>insufficient data to calculate an effect size</i>).
manualised curricula: language stimulation methods ($n = 4$)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kauman, 1972, $d = 0.28c$; • Goodson et al., 2010, $d = 0.14$; • Assel et al., 2007: 2: $d = -0.52$ effect varied by setting • Justice et al., 2008: no significant effect
SLT involvement in teaching ($n = 2$)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gillam et al., 2014: narrative competence ($d = 0.82$); specifically targeted vocabulary ($d = 1.02$) • Hadley et al., 2000: $d = 0.3c$
large-scale PD ($n = 1$)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Snow et al., 2016: narrative competence: $d = 0.33$;

The more structured multiple strategy IRB interventions also yielded large positive effects indicating there are many effective approaches which can have a positive effect on children's expressive vocabulary. However, effects may be limited to knowledge of the target words on researcher designed tests only and may not transfer to general vocabulary ability as measured by a standardised measure of vocabulary knowledge. The two studies which included both measures reported very small or no effects (Neuman & Kaefer, 2018, $d = 0.03$); Gonzalez et al., 2010: no effect) on general vocabulary development.

Silverman's (2007) study examined three variations of IBR on vocabulary: (a) 'analytical instruction' involving scrutiny of target words in contexts beyond the participants own; (b) 'contextual instruction' which emphasised links between participants' experiences and target vocabulary; and (c) 'anchored instruction' which combined analytical instruction with phonological and orthographic exploration of target words. Significant effects were found for two of the variations: analytical instruction (0.58) and anchored instruction (0.94). Silverman's 2013 studies examining the impact on vocabulary of single viewing and multiple viewing of TV programmes reported minimal effects. Such findings highlight the complexity of vocabulary instruction and the need for purposeful multi-faceted approaches.

The findings in relation to conversation-based approaches *'were surprising given the extensive literature supporting the utility of social-interactionist theories of language development (Hoff, 2006) in the early years'* (Dobinson & Dockrell, p.17). Researchers surmised that the lack of effect may have been due to the expertise of the students who interacted with the children and likely highlight the need for professional development and structure. Two studies involving speech and language therapists working in collaboration with teachers highlight the potential of cross-disciplinary expertise in addressing oral language issues. The four studies implementing manualised curricula had mixed outcomes. They had most impact in Head Start classrooms staffed by less qualified personnel and no impact in classrooms staffed by qualified teachers. Finally, though not all studies provided sufficient detail on duration and intensity, it is likely these dimensions are also important factors in the success of oral language interventions.

Education Endowment Foundation Review (updated 2021) included 20 studies (11 meta-analyses and 9 single studies) and largely corroborated Dobinson & Dockrell's (2021) findings. The EEF also broadened the scope to include studies examining the impact of oral language on language development across the curriculum (e.g. Alexander, 2012; Hanley et al., 2015) and dialogic teaching approaches on reading comprehension (e.g. Murphy et al., 2009; Guthrie et al. 2007; Elleman et al., 2009; Jay et al., 2017; Styles & Bradshaw, 2015; Styles et al. 2014) The studies explored:

- targeted reading aloud and book discussion with young children;
- explicitly extending pupils' spoken vocabulary;
- the use of structured questioning to develop reading comprehension;
- the use of purposeful, curriculum-focused, dialogue and interaction.

This body of research is rooted in socio-cultural perspectives on learning and apprenticeship models (Vygotsky, 1978; Bakhtin 1981, 1986; Rogoff, 1990) which recognise the role of interaction in shaping the construction of knowledge and higher-order thinking through regular participation in a literary community. The average weighted effect size for the studies included in the EEF review (0.37) indicates the potential and importance of dialogic approaches which link reading and oral language. Such effects translate into an average gain of six months' additional progress on pupil outcomes (see also Kennedy & Shiel, 2022) for differential impact on children in educational disadvantaged contexts) and are mediated by the level of professional development provided and the degree to which interventions are matched to curriculum and learners' current stage of development. Interestingly, similar results were found for both teachers and teaching

assistants indicating that with appropriate professional development those with lower qualifications can be supported to work effectively with children on oral language and reading. Additional benefits to dialogic interventions are the improved classroom climate and fewer discipline issues reported in some of the studies. The Murphy et al. (2009) meta-analysis is particularly noteworthy as it examined the efficacy of a variety of approaches to oral language and reading which they grouped into three perspectives or stances:

- **Efferent stance** e.g. Rosenblatt 1978: Instructional Conversations (Goldenburg, 1993), Questioning the Author (Beck & McKeown, 2006) Junior Great Books (1987)
- **Aesthetic-expressive stance** e.g. Rosenblatt 1978; Murphy et al., 2009: Book Clubs (Raphael & McMahon, 1994), Literature Circles (Short and Pierce, 1990), Grand Conversations (Eeds & Wells, 1989)
- **Critical/analytical stance** e.g. Freebody & Luke, 1996: Paidea seminar (Billings & Fitzgerald, 2002), Collaborative Reasoning (Anderson et al., 1998), Philosophy for children (Sharp, 1995)

Their analysis revealed that discussion approaches are not *'created equal, nor are they equally powerful at increasing students' high-level comprehension of text'* (p.761). Of particular importance is the finding that it was easier to impact the amount and distribution of talk (particularly of students) in the classroom than on comprehension. Not surprisingly, the emphasis of the particular discussion approach used in the study was reflected in effects found. For example, if the approach emphasised an expressive stance children improved their ability to discuss their personal responses to text. Findings also indicated that when teachers promoted higher-level talk about text on a literary and critical level it always predicted achievement, regardless of grade level and almost always in relation to socio-economic status. Challenges identified with implementation included the difficulty in moving teachers from away from controlling the discussion through rapid-fire recitation style questioning towards more dialogic thoughtful responses. However, authentic teacher questions and uptake by students to explore ideas, to the extent that they were used, suppressed potentially negative effects of macro variables such as tracking, SES, race, and ethnicity.

Oral Language and Writing

No specific systematic reviews were found exploring the relationship between oral language and writing development. Kennedy and Shiel (2019) in a review of the literature on writing pedagogy highlighted the important role of oral language in supporting writing

development. Their review noted that though less-widely researched, there is evidence that oral language is critical to writing development (Dockrell et al., 2015; Van der Heide 2017) and that writing ‘has a complex relationship to talk’ (NCTE, 2016). Like writing, talk varies according to each discipline’s structure, goals, ways of thinking and learning, vocabulary, and texts. ‘*Accountable talk*’ has also been found to support disciplinary learning (Michaels, O’Connor, Hall & Resnick, 2002). As Zygouris-Coe (2002) asserts ‘according to this type of talk, everyone is accountable to the development of meaning by all and for all’ and accountable to knowledge building, providing sufficient evidence for assertions and rigorous thinking. The teacher’s role is to model, promote and facilitate disciplinary talk.

In classrooms where teachers adopt a process-based and workshop-based approaches to writing, there are many opportunities for social interaction and oral language to be developed. Children can discuss their writing topics, collaborate in the writing of texts, work together to revise and edit a piece of work, and share their writing product with the whole class in share session through the Authors’ Chair which often occurs at the end of a writing workshop. Guthrie and Anderson (1999) suggest that, ‘*when students can talk to each other about their writing, they learn an acute sense of audience and authorship*’ (p. 36). Students may be encouraged to listen for details, ask questions and state what they appreciated about the piece of writing. Feedback should increase in sophistication as children progress through primary school and they should be able to notice examples of craft mini-lessons in their peers’ writing and respond to them using appropriate academic language. When oral language permeates daily share sessions, it also cultivates positive writer identities and enhances students’ understanding of writing as a social and communicative act (Graham et al., 2012a; Kennedy & Shiel, 2019).

Van der Heide (2017) adopting a genre theory and socio-cultural lens in relation to argumentative writing (p. 342) contends that ‘*learning to write should be a social process in which students learn to make the writing moves of a genre by talking about writing with others and through trying out and hearing talk moves in conversation*’. As Kennedy & Shiel (2019) highlight, the ways in which teachers are able to structure talk and provide opportunities for students to talk within writing workshops is pivotal. Teachers need a repertoire of skills to facilitate such talk including higher-order questioning, prompting, revoicing, recasting contributions and employing wait time for students to formulate their thoughts. They further highlight ways in which students can engage in authentic oral language activities e.g. in considering an oral presentation rather than

a written publication in publishing their writing; and in using *'technologies such as voice recording apps on smartphones and audio editing tools...as students create podcasts, videos, or other multimedia work in which they share their writing through oral production'* (NCTE, 2016, p.15).

Combining Reading and Writing Instruction

The influence of reading on writing and vice versa is considered to be bi-directional (Shanahan, 1984). A number of meta-analyses and systematic reviews have explored the evidence base on the efficacy of instructional approaches balancing attention to reading and writing. Drawing on 89 experimental studies Graham et al. (2018a) investigated if literacy programs balancing attention to reading and writing instruction improved students' reading and writing performance. Average weighted effect size means were significant for overall reading measures ($d=0.39$) and for measures of reading comprehension (ES= 0.39), decoding (ES= 0.53) or reading vocabulary (ES= 0.35). The programs reviewed were also found to statistically enhance writing performance. Average weighted effect sizes were computed for overall writing ($d= .37$) and for writing quality (ES= .47), writing mechanics (ES= 0.18) and writing output as measured as number of words written. (ES=0 .69)

The second study (Graham et al., 2018b) examined the effect of reading interventions on students' writing performance. Teaching reading strengthened writing, resulting in statistically significant average weighted effect for an overall measure of writing (ES = 0.57) and on specific aspects of writing including writing quality (ES = 0.63), words written (ES = 0.37), or spelling (ES = 0.56). Furthermore, the impact of teaching reading on writing was maintained over time (ES = 0.37). A further insight was the finding that having students read text or observe others interact with text also enhanced writing performance, producing a statistically significant impact on an overall measure of writing (ES = 0.35) and specific measures of writing quality (ES = 0.44) and spelling (ES = 0.28). These findings provide support that reading interventions can also enhance students' writing performance.

An earlier meta-analysis (Graham & Hebert, 2011) involving 85 studies sought to answer three specific questions:

- Does writing about material read enhance students' comprehension?
- Does writing skills instruction strengthen students' reading skills?
- Does increasing how much students write improve how they read?

Positive effect sizes were reported for all three questions and the quality of studies was rated high. Overall effects were robust and positive for studies providing opportunities for students to write about reading material regardless of reading measure utilised (e.g. 11 studies using standardised reading comprehension tests had an average effect of 0.37 while 55 studies using researcher-devised tests had an average effect of 0.50). This held true for narrative and expository texts (grades 2-12) and across disciplines (language arts, social studies and Science). Studies included primary (25%), middle (34%) and high school students (41%). Writing activities that involved students in summary writing (ES= 0.50), note-taking (0.42) and asking or answering questions about reading yielded effect sizes ranging from 0.28 to 0.68 (variation was mostly due to between study factors). In 12 studies, average positive effects (ES= 0.64) were found for the reading comprehension of weaker readers and writers on (researcher developed tests) signifying the particular benefits of such instruction to lower-achieving students.

Strong evidence was found for the effect of writing skills instruction on reading for students in grades 4-12. Writing instruction in these studies comprised a range of approaches including process writing, text structure and paragraph/sentence instruction resulting in statistically significant average weighted effect sizes (0.33: 12 studies using norm referenced reading measures; 0.27: five studies using researcher devised reading tests). In grades 1-7, even higher effect sizes were achieved for reading fluency (0.66) where writing instruction comprised either sentence combining or spelling while in grades 1-5, six studies on spelling had strong effects on word reading (0.62). Finally, increasing amount of writing positively influences reading comprehension in grades 1-6 (6 studies with average weighted effect size 0.35).

Graham's (2020) review of the Science of Reading and Science of Writing, highlights that *'teaching recommendations drawn from science often have failed to take advantage of how writing and reading can support each other'* (p.36). His review highlights limitations of the National Reading Panel (NRP) report (National Institutes of Children's Health and Development, 2000) which prioritised reading and did not include research on writing practices that have been shown to improve reading (e.g. writing about material read, writing as a means for becoming a better reader, and writing instruction that increases knowledge benefitting reading (e.g. Graham & Hebert, 2011; Graham & Santangelo, 2014, Graham et al., 2018a, 2018b). Graham (2020) makes a strong case for greater integration of both reading and writing in research and practice, citing multiple studies and seminal papers on theories highlighting connections between reading and

writing including shared knowledge theory (Fitzgerald & Shanahan, 2000); rhetorical relations theory (Rubin, 1984) and functional theory (Langer & Applebee, 1987; Shanahan, 2016).

Jouhar and Rupley (2021) included 13 studies in their systematic review of the literature on reading-writing connections based on independent reading and independent writing. It is important to note, that a limitation of these studies is that the independent writing was not entirely independent, in the sense that there were varying degrees of instruction (e.g. mini-lessons regarding the process of writing and optimal structure of text: Crowhurst, 1990, 1991; Dana et al., 1991; Hayes & Bahruth, 1985) and feedback (Hayes & Bahruth, 1985; Ramey, 1989; Lee & Schallert, 2016) so it was not a case of free writing. As noted in earlier sections of this paper, independent writing is a feature of current writing workshop and process-based approaches to writing which include substantial levels of instruction and feedback.

Analysis revealed five studies in which independent reading experimental groups statistically significantly outperformed control groups in overall writing quality (Elley & Mangubhai, 1983; Hafiz & Tudor, 1989, 1990; Lee & Hsu, 2009; Tsang, 1996) and in three studies a statistically significant increase in writing output at posttest was reported for experimental groups (Hafiz & Tudor, 1990; Lai, 1993; Lee & Hsu, 2009). The findings obtained from seven studies *'conclusively suggest that independent reading enhances overall narrative and descriptive writing quality, and increases output, mechanics, spelling accuracy, content, grammatical accuracy, and text organization'* (p.136). In relation to the influence of independent reading on writing vocabulary (measured by vocabulary ratio, length of T-units and sentences, and sentence structure) statistical significance was not found highlighting the need for explicit instruction in word choice if writing vocabulary is to be influenced. Finally, independent writing was found to improve literal reading comprehension for beginning, low-performing and at risk students' reading attainment and both literal and inferential reading for normally achieving students. The review points to the value of including independent reading and independent writing opportunities for students as part of literacy frameworks that also include systematic instruction in reading and writing (see also systematic review on educational disadvantage: Shiel & Kennedy, 2022)

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Biographies

Dr Eithne Kennedy is an Associate Professor in the School of Language, Literacy and Early Childhood Education, DCU Institute of Education. She is the Programme Chair of the Master of Education in Literacy Professional Practice and teaches on a range of literacy modules at undergraduate level. She is the recipient of the International Literacy Association’s Outstanding

Dissertation Award for her doctoral thesis: *Improving literacy achievement in a disadvantaged primary school: Empowering classroom teachers through professional development*. As director of the *Write to Read* research initiative, she collaborates with schools in disadvantaged areas to create powerful literacy environments that motivate and engage children as readers, writers and thinkers. She is one of the lead authors of NCCA desktop reviews of research on literacy education in the context of the redevelopment of the primary language curriculum (2012, 2019) and served on the NCCA Curriculum Development Group (2012-2015). She is a member of the Federation of European Literacy Associations special interest group: *The Initial Teaching of Literacy Across Europe*. She has served as one of the Irish partners on the European Commission's ELINET research consortium on literacy policy and practice and the *European Cooperation in Science and Technology Project* which investigated the digital and multimodal practices of young children (birth to age 8).

Dr Tara Concannon-Gibney is an Assistant Professor in the School of Language, Literacy and Early Childhood Education at the Institute of Education, Dublin City University where she lectures in the area of literacy at undergraduate and postgraduate level. A former primary school teacher, she has worked with pre-service and in-service teachers in Ireland and in New York for almost twenty years. Prior to joining D.C.U. in 2017, she was programme coordinator of the B.Sc. in Early Childhood at Marino Institute of Education (Dublin) where she lectured in literacy and Early Childhood. She is a past president of the Literacy Association of Ireland and is currently the Irish representative on the Federation of European Literacy Association's executive committee. She has published in numerous national and international peer-reviewed journals and is the author of *Teaching Essential Literacy Skills: A guide for students and teachers* (Routledge).

Dr Bernadette Dwyer is an Associate Professor in the school of Language, Literacy and Early Childhood Education where she lectures and researches in the area of Literacy. She has published refereed articles in high ranking journals, chapters in books, commissioned reports, and has edited conference proceedings. Her most recent book publication is *Using technology to improve reading and learning*. Bernadette is a regular presenter at both national and international conferences and has given a range of invited keynote addresses at conferences around the world. Bernadette has been awarded a number of awards including the DCU President's award for Engagement in the Community(2016) and the Technology in Reading Research Award (2017) by the TILE-SIG of the International Literacy Association. Bernadette served on the International Literacy Association (ILA) board from 2013-2016 and was elected as President of ILA 2018. She chaired the International Taskforce on the systematic review of the literature pertaining to *Children's Rights to Read*. and *Children's Rights to Excellent Literacy Instruction*. Bernadette is currently engaged in research in the areas of multimodal/ digital literacies; inquiry-based learning; and disciplinary literacies.

Appendix A: Search Strategy

Overview –The overarching focus of the search strategy in this section was the development of literacy skills of Irish language speakers and learners, and linguistically diverse learners. The three broad categories of student are; (i) learners of Irish as a second language (L2), (ii) emergent speakers and speakers of Irish in Irish-medium settings (L1), and (iii) English as additional language (EAL) and migrant students who speak neither English or Irish at home.

Research Questions

1. What systematic reviews or meta-analyses have been conducted that are relevant to the area: Oral language, reading, writing?
2. How can learners in K-6 be supported in developing reading skills within literacy?
3. How can learners in K-6 be supported in developing writing skills within literacy?
4. How can learners in K-6 be supported in developing oral language within literacy?

Key Search Terms

In searching for suitable systematic reviews, meta-analyses and other literature to answer the questions above we searched the following databases using the key search terms described for each database.

1. LITERACY or reading or reading skills or literacy skills or writing or writing skills or dialogue skills or "oral language" (as a Subject Heading)
2. and k-6 OR elementary OR primary (as a free text search)
3. AND meta-analysis OR systematic review OR best evidence (as a free text search)

Reading Comprehension
Oral reading fluency
Reading Vocabulary
Early literacy skills
Writing
Oral language
Achievement
Motivation & engagement

Google Scholar: LITERACY or reading or 'reading skills' or 'literacy skills' or writing or 'writing skills' or 'dialogue skills' or "oral language" AND k-6 OR elementary OR primary AND meta-analysis OR 'systematic review' OR 'best evidence'

(literacy or reading or reading skills or literacy skills) AND AB "reading comprehension" AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or best evidence) AND (k-6 or elementary or primary)

(literacy or reading or reading skills or literacy skills) AND AB "oral reading fluency" AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or best evidence) AND (k-6 or elementary or primary)

(literacy or reading or reading skills or literacy skills) AND AB "reading vocabulary" AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or best evidence) AND (k-6 or elementary or primary)

(literacy or reading or reading skills or literacy skills) AND AB "early literacy skills" AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or best evidence) AND (k-6 or elementary or primary)

(literacy or reading or reading skills or literacy skills) AND AB 'motivation and engagement' AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or best evidence) AND (k-6 or elementary or primary)

(literacy or writing or writing skills or literacy skills) AND AB "writing" AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or best evidence) AND (k-6 or elementary or primary)

SEARCH 1

Writing skills or Writing ability or Writing development or Writing improvement or Writing instruction or Writing intervention (Title)

OR Writing skills or Writing ability or Writing development or Writing improvement or Writing instruction or Writing intervention (Abstract)

SEARCH 2

S1 AND Meta-analysis or Systematic review

Key Data Sources Consulted

Note: Literature in the systematic review should be from 2011 onwards, although reference may also be made to earlier seminal works. Examples:

- SCOPUS, EBSCO, ERIC Linguistic/Language Behavior Abstracts, MathEduc.
- Google Scholar (to identify articles that might not appear in a systematic review)
- Handbooks in the field published since 2011
- 'Grey literature' (e.g., reports published by international/ national organisations /government – UNESCO, OECD, Dept of Education, NCCA etc.)
- International Database of Education Systematic Reviews (IDESR)

PRISMA Chart

*Records excluded following blind review by two reviewers using COVIDENCE

Reading Comprehension					
Title of Article and Authors, Year of Publication	No. of studies	Effect sizes (If available)	Aspect of reading:	Age range / Level(s)	Findings
Clinton, V., Taylor, T., Bajpayee, S., Davison, M. L., Carlson, S. E., & Seipel, B. (2020). Inferential Comprehension Differences between Narrative and Expository Texts: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. <i>Reading and Writing: An Interdisciplinary Journal</i> , 33(9), 2223–2248.	18 reports 19 studies	Scores on measures of inferential comprehension were higher for narrative texts than expository texts ($g = 0.36$, $p = 0.02$).	Narrative and expository text		This effect did not vary depending on whether inferential comprehension was assessed during or after reading, whether the texts for each genre were matched for readability, whether the reader was an adult or child, and whether the inference connected different ideas in the text (text connecting) or the text to background knowledge (knowledge based).
Cao, Y., & Kim, Y.-S. G. (2021). Is Retell a Valid Measure of Reading Comprehension? <i>Grantee Submission</i> , 32.	23	Retell and RC:ES =0.46 significant negative moderating effecting higher grades $Q_m = 6.57$, $df = 1$		Grades 1-12	Meta-analysis evaluating the relation between retell and other measures of reading comprehension showed a moderate relation between retell and other measures of reading comprehension, $r = 0.46$. Relation was stronger when reading comprehension was measured by cloze or maze tasks than when measured using a multiple-choice format The relation between ‘oral’ retell and reading comprehension was stronger with a greater number of prompts provided during retell tests. In contrast, results did not differ by other features of retell such as reading mode (oral or silent), text genres of retell (narrative or informational), or use of different oral retell evaluation methods (e.g., number of words or ideas, overall quality). The authors urge caution in using retell as the sole measure of reading comprehension given the moderate magnitude of the relation between retell and other measures of reading comprehension.
Davis, D. S. (2013). Multiple Comprehension Strategies Instruction in the Intermediate Grades: Three Remarks about Content and Pedagogy in the			Strategy instruction		Conceptual review of Multiple Comprehension Strategies Instruction (MCSI). Review of a range of MSCI approaches and models. There are shared pedagogical features across these multifaceted instructional approaches but no one dominant approach features in all. Most MCSI models use a scaffolded instructional sequence based on the gradual release of

Intervention Literature. <i>Review of Education</i> , 1(2), 194–224.					responsibility model (Duke & Pearson, 2002). The author claims that independent and self-regulated reading practices are underemphasized in the MCSI literature despite strong conceptual roots in self-regulation and metacognitive learning theory. Many MCSI studies present a proceduralised view of strategic reading, characterized by repeated use of common strategies taught to students in a prescribed sequence. The author espouses the need for helping students become more intentional and reflective as to the identification of reading goals and selection of strategies to meet those goals.
Davoudi, M., & Sadeghi, N. A. (2015). A Systematic Review of Research on Questioning as a High-level Cognitive Strategy. <i>English Language Teaching</i> , 8(10), p76.	40		Questioning		The findings of the in-depth review reveal the indispensable role of teacher and student questioning in facilitating critical thinking, writing ability, reading comprehension, subject matter learning, metacognitive skills, and scaffolding learning process
Dong, Y., Wu, S. X.-Y., Dong, W.-Y., & Tang, Y. (2020). The Effects of Home Literacy Environment on Children’s Reading Comprehension Development: A Meta-Analysis. <i>Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice</i> , 20(2), 63–82.	59		HLE effect on reading comprehension		A rich home literacy environment (HLE) fosters students' academic achievement. This study examined the effects of HLE factors on children's reading comprehension. Results of the meta-analysis indicated three main findings. First, the overall positive correlation between HLE and children's reading comprehension was moderate ([zeta] = 0.32). Second, sampling area, type of home literacy resource and parental involvement styles did not show a significant interaction effect between each HLE factor and children's reading comprehension. Third, parents' involvement and literacy expectations of children had a significantly higher correlation with children's reading comprehension than home literacy resources did. Findings of this study suggest that parental literacy activities involvement and parental literacy expectations contribute more to children's literacy knowledge enhancement.
Elleman, A. M. (2017). Examining the Impact of Inference Instruction on the	25			k-12	Inference ability is considered central to discourse processing and has been shown to be important across models of reading comprehension

<p>Literal and Inferential Comprehension of Skilled and Less Skilled Readers: A Meta-Analytic Review.</p> <p><i>Journal of Educational Psychology</i>, 109(6), 761–781.</p>				<p>Although skilled and less skilled readers responded similarly on general and inference outcomes, less skilled readers benefitted more on literal outcomes. Findings suggest that students can increase their inference ability and that less skilled readers gain the extra benefit of increases in literal comprehension. Findings also suggest that instruction provided in small groups is beneficial for increasing readers' inferential understanding of text. Results showed that inference instruction was effective for increasing students' general comprehension, $d = 0.58$, inferential comprehension, $d = 0.68$, and literal comprehension, $d = 0.28$. Although skilled and less skilled readers responded similarly on general and inference outcomes, less skilled readers benefitted more on literal outcomes, $d = 0.97$, than skilled readers, $d = 0.06$. Instruction in small groups more beneficial</p>
<p>Eun-Young Jeon, & Day, R. R. (2016). The effectiveness of ER on reading proficiency: A meta-analysis. <i>Reading in a Foreign Language</i>, 28(2), 246–265.</p>	49		Extensive reading	<p>A meta-analysis was performed to investigate the impact of extensive reading (ER) on reading proficiency. Small to medium effect was found. a higher effect was found in the adults than in the children and adolescents group. EFL/ESL focus</p>
<p>Follmer, D. J. (2018). Executive Function and Reading Comprehension: A Meta-Analytic Review. <i>Educational Psychologist</i>, 53(1), 42–60.</p>		Results (N = 6,673) R=0.36	Executive function and RC	<p>This article presents a meta-analytic review of the relation between executive function and reading comprehension. Moderator analyses suggested that correlations between executive function and reading comprehension did not vary systematically by age range, type of executive function measure used, type of reading comprehension measure used, or whether the study was a dissertation or a published article but did vary by type of executive function examined in the studies.</p>
<p>Graham, S., Liu, X., Aitken, A., Ng, C., Bartlett, B., Harris, K. R., & Holzapfel, J. (2018). Effectiveness of Literacy Programs Balancing Reading and Writing Instruction: A Meta-</p>		reading comprehension (ES = 0.39), decoding (ES = 0.53), or reading vocabulary (ES = 0.35). writing quality (ES = 0.47),	Reading/Writing Connection	<p>Reading and writing are critical to students' success in and outside of school. Because they draw on common sources of knowledge and cognitive processes, involve meaning making, and can be used conjointly to accomplish. Findings demonstrated that literacy programs balancing reading and writing instruction can strengthen reading and writing and that the two skills can be learned together profitably.</p>

Analysis. <i>Reading Research Quarterly</i> , 53(3), 279–304.		writing mechanics (ES = 0.18), or writing output (ES = 0.69).			
Guo, D., Zhang, S., Wright, K. L., & McTigue, E. M. (2020). Do You Get the Picture? A Meta-Analysis of the Effect of Graphics on Reading Comprehension. <i>AERA Open</i> , 6(1)	39	graphics had a moderate overall positive effect (Hedges's $g = 0.39$) on students' reading comprehension, regardless of grade	Effect of graphics on RC		No significant difference for graphic when compared to mixed graphics, pictures had a greater effect on comprehension. Additionally, compared with true and false assessments, graphics differentially benefited students' comprehension on open-ended comprehension assessments and mixed format assessments.
Ray, M. N., & Meyer, B. J. F. (2011). Individual Differences in Children's Knowledge of Expository Text Structures: A Review of Literature. <i>International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education</i> , 4(1), 67–82.					Review explores empirical research of individual differences in younger readers' knowledge and use of expository text structures. The goal of this review is to explore the influence of reader and text characteristics in order to better understand the instructional needs of elementary school readers Analysis of reviewed literature suggests that readers of all ages may benefit from explicit instruction in text structure, particularly less-skilled comprehenders. Focus text structure instruction on highly structured texts (comparison, causation, problem-and-solution.
Reynolds, D. (2017). Interactional Scaffolding for Reading Comprehension: A Systematic Review. <i>Literacy Research: Theory, Method, and Practice</i> , 66(1), 135–156.	57			k-5	Review employed theories of scaffolding and reading comprehension to establish a theoretical framework, on interactional scaffolding. Themes emerging suggested a diversity in taxonomies of scaffolding, a focus on contingency, the influence of contextual and mediational resources in shaping scaffolding approaches and pitfalls when scaffolding is not optimal.
Silverman, R. D., Johnson, E., Keane, K., & Khanna, S. (2020). Beyond Decoding: A Meta-Analysis of the Effects of Language Comprehension Interventions on K–5 Students' Language and Literacy Outcomes.	43		Language comprehension		Findings suggest positive effects on custom measures of vocabulary, listening comprehension, and reading comprehension but not on standardized measures of these outcomes. Results also indicate positive effects for English learners and promise for multicomponent interventions and those that include technology

<i>Reading Research Quarterly</i> , 55, S207–S233.					
Wright, T. S., & Cervetti, G. N. (2017). A Systematic Review of the Research on Vocabulary Instruction That Impacts Text Comprehension. <i>Reading Research Quarterly</i> , 52(2), 203–226.	36		Vocabulary instruction impact on Reading comprehension		The study is a systematic review of vocabulary interventions with comprehension outcomes. Their findings led to four major themes: (1) Teaching of word meanings supported comprehension of text containing the target words in almost all cases; (2) instruction that focused on some active processing was typically more impactful than a definition or a dictionary method for supporting comprehension of text containing the target words, but we do not know how much instruction is sufficient; (3) there is very limited evidence that direct teaching of word meanings, even long-term, multifaceted interventions of large numbers of words, can improve generalized comprehension; and (4) there is currently no empirical evidence that instruction in one or two strategies for solving word meanings will impact generalized comprehension. However, studies that actively teach students to monitor their understanding of vocabulary and to use multiple, flexible strategies for solving word meanings are a promising area for future research.
Hwang, H., Cabell, S. Q., & Joyner, R. E. (2021). Effects of Integrated Literacy and Content-area Instruction on Vocabulary and Comprehension in the Elementary Years: A Meta-analysis. <i>Scientific Studies of Reading</i> , 1–27.	35 quasi (experimental studies)	Effect Size (ES) Vocabulary =0.91; Comprehension ES=0.40; Content knowledge ES=0.89		k-5	Results suggest that integrated literacy and content area instruction has potential to enhance vocabulary and comprehension in elementary school while concurrently building both science and social studies knowledge
Toste, Jessica R.; Didion, Lisa; Peng, Peng; Filderman, Marissa J.; McClelland, Amanda M.	132	motivation and reading, $r = 0.22$, $p < 0.001$	Motivation and reading	.k-12	Meta-analytic review to investigate the relation between motivation and reading achievement Earlier reading is a stronger predictor of later motivation than motivation is of reading. Taken together, the findings from this meta-analysis

A Meta-Analytic Review of the Relations Between Motivation and Reading Achievement for K–12 Students.					provide a better understanding of how motivational processes relate to reading performance, which has important implications for developing effective instructional practices and fostering students' active engagement in reading.
Unrau, N. J., Rueda, R., Son, E., Polanin, J. R., Lundeen, R. J., & Muraszewski, A. K. (2018). Can Reading Self-Efficacy Be Modified? A Meta-Analysis of the Impact of Interventions on Reading Self-Efficacy. <i>Review of Educational Research</i> , 88(2), 167	30 studies		Motivation and Reading	K-College	Meta-analysis suggesting strong correlation between reading comprehension and self-efficacy. Significant moderators of effect sizes included grade level, number of sources shaping self-efficacy. Challenges included defining and measuring self-efficacy, with variance between the studies.
Phonics, Phonological Awareness and Morphology					
Title of Article and Authors, Year of Publication	No. of studies	Effect sizes (If available)	Aspect of reading:	Age range / Grade	Findings
Bowers, J. S. (2020). Reconsidering the evidence that systematic phonics is more effective than alternative methods of reading instruction <i>Educational Psychology Review</i> 2020;32(3):681-705	12			Lower primary	Phonics is important but little or no evidence that systematic phonics is better than standard alternative methods used in schools. -teachers and researchers should consider alternative methods of reading instruction for example emphasising morphology and the interrelation between phonology, morphology, and etymology
European Eurydice Report (2011). <i>Teaching Reading in Europe: Contexts, Policies and Practices</i> , Brussels: Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency					Phonological and phonemic awareness, phonics and reading fluency as most influential factors in the early stages of reading development. phonological awareness can benefit later word reading and can have an impact on children at risk of reading difficulties highlights the need for a clear programme or plan' (p32) for phonics rather than 'more sporadic attention' (p.32) -systematic phonics instruction has a positive impact on the reading development of young and struggling reading

<p>Foorman, B., Beyler, N., Borradaile, K., Coyne, M., Denton, C., Dimino, J., ... Wissel, S. (2016). Foundational skills to support reading for understanding in kindergarten through 3rd grade (NCEE 2016-4008). Washington, DC: National Center for Education Evaluation and Regional Assistance, Institute of Education Sciences, U.S. Department of Education.</p>				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -importance of teaching academic language skills, including the use of inferential and narrative language, and vocabulary knowledge to children. -combine instruction on reading skills with instruction on academic language skills so that students will understand the meaning of the words, sentences, and text they read. -children need to develop awareness of the segments of sounds in speech and how they link to letters. This includes phonemic awareness and knowledge of letter names and sounds. -explicitly teach students to segment syllables, onset-rimes, and phonemes in spoken words and how these units of sound correspond to letters. At the same time, teach the distinctive features of letters so that students can distinguish one letter from another. -children need to be taught to decode words, analyze word parts, and write and recognize words. Students should be taught sound-spelling patterns and morphological elements such as prefixes and suffixes. Children should be taught how to encode as well as decode so that they can recognize them quickly and use them in their writing. - All students should read connected text every day to support reading accuracy, fluency, and comprehension. -In an intervention, select instructional-level texts should be used to allow students to practice accurate decoding and encoding, and reread the texts to build fluency.
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<p>Goodwin, A.P. & Ahn, S. (2013) A meta-Analysis of morphological interventions in English: Effects on literacy outcomes for school-age children, <i>Scientific Studies of Reading</i>, 17:4, 257-285, DOI: 10.1080/10888438.2012.689791</p>	30	<p>Moderate overall (d = 0.32); significant and moderate intervention effects on morphological knowledge (d = 0.44), phonological awareness (d = 0.48), vocabulary (d = 0.34), decoding (d = 0.59), and spelling (d = 0.30) but not on reading comprehension or fluency.</p>			<p>-largest effects were for decoding, phonological awareness, and morphological knowledge - moderate effects for vocabulary and spelling -lack of overall effect on fluency and reading comprehension - various types of morphological instruction support literacy achievement</p>
<p>Invernizzi, M. & Tortorelli, L. (2013). Phonological awareness and alphabet knowledge: The foundations of early reading, in D.M. Barone, & M. Mallette, M. <i>Best practices in early literacy instruction</i>. New York, NY: Guilford Press.</p>					<p>-phonological awareness and alphabet knowledge must be explicitly taught, need ample opportunities to apply this skill, reciprocal relationship between phonological awareness, alphabet knowledge and oral vocabulary -significance of the developmental progression (words in sentences, rhyming across words, syllables within words, onset/rime and phonemes) in planning instruction</p>
<p>Torgerson, C., Brooks, G., Gascoine, L. & Higgin, S. (2019.) Phonics: reading policy and the evidence of effectiveness from a systematic ‘tertiary’ review <i>Research Papers in Education</i>, 34:2, 208-238,</p>	12	<p>Statistically significant positive effects: phonics instruction on at least one reading outcome found in (10); ES moderate effects; Non-significant positive effects in 2.</p>		Pre-primary through to adult, most at primary level	<p>-Include systematic phonics instruction for younger readers -Evidence is not clear enough to stipulate which phonics approach is best - insufficient evidence to justify a ‘phonics only’ teaching policy (many studies have added phonics to whole language approaches, calling it ‘balanced instruction’) -clarification in relation to phonics ‘dosage’ remains</p>

Suggate, S. P. (2016). A meta-analysis of the long-term effects of phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, and reading comprehension interventions <i>Journal of Learning Disabilities</i> , 49(1):77-96	71	posttest effect sizes indicated effects (dw = 0.37) that decreased to follow-up (dw = 0.22);		Pre-school/ elementary	-comprehension and phonemic awareness interventions showed good maintenance of effect that transferred to non-targeted skills, whereas phonics and fluency interventions, and those for preschool and kindergarten children, tended not to. -preschool and kindergarten interventions should target phonemic awareness alone, decoding skills should be left to Grades 1 and 2. -Grades 1/2, fluency and mixed interventions are recommended, but effects may not transfer well to reading comprehension.
Reading Vocabulary					
Title of Article and Authors, Year of Publication	No. of studies	Effect sizes (If available)	Aspect of reading:	Age range	Findings
Cregan, A. (2019). Promoting oral language in the primary school. Dublin: NCCA.					importance of sustained emphasis on development of vocabulary -effective vocabulary teaching involves selectively choosing target words to teach, explicitly teaching target vocabulary while also promoting word consciousness which encourages the development of implicit, incidental vocabulary knowledge, providing multiple encounters with target vocabulary, explicitly teaching morphemic analysis to extend word knowledge, use multi-sensory techniques to help anchor word knowledge (Lane & Allen, 2010; Flynt & Brozo, 2008)
Grover, V. (2017). Fostering vocabulary in early childhood education in N. Kucirkova, C. E. Snow, V. Grøver, & C. McBride (Eds) <i>The Routledge international handbook of early literacy education: a contemporary guide to literacy teaching and interventions in a global context</i> . New York: Routledge.					- importance of explicitly teaching word meaning, need for review and multiple exposures (Penno et al. (2002) Beck and McKeown (2007) Nielsen and Friesen (2012) -extended discussion resulted in greater word learning than either incidental exposure or embedded instruction. Coyne et al. (2009) - semantic instruction or anchored instruction (paying attention to spoken or written forms of the word) was more effective than restricting word instruction to defining words in kindergarten. Silverman (2007)

					<p>-Teachers' use of extra-textual talk during shared reading in preschool improved children's vocabulary knowledge (Zucker et al. (2013))</p> <p>-exposure to challenging, inferential talk during preschool book reading had a positive effect of vocabulary development Dickinson and Porche (2011)</p>
Hairrell , A., Rupley, W. & Simmons, D. (2011) The state of vocabulary research, <i>Literacy Research and Instruction</i> , 50:4, 253-271, DOI: 10.1080/19388071.2010.514036	24	<p>Contextual analysis: $\eta^2 = .002-.035$; $d = -.01-3.17$,</p> <p>Morphological analysis: $d = -1.00-1.58$,</p> <p>Semantics: $d = 0.55-3.17$,</p> <p>Mnemonics: $d=2.85$, Multiple strategies: $d = -0.12-2.85$</p> <p>Metacognitive strategies: $d = .161-1.94$, Visual cues: $\eta^2 p = .55$</p>		2-8 grade	<p>-contextual analysis instruction increases vocabulary learning</p> <p>-when contextual and morphological analysis were combined in overall analysis, effect size for morphology over the combined effect was $d = 0.59$.</p> <p>-when semantic strategies were part of a multicomponent vocabulary program, there were positive effects</p> <p>-semantic instruction was effective with students with limited vocabulary knowledge (Apthorp, 2006) , created more long-term, resilient knowledge</p> <p>-brief, explicit, teacher-led lessons on relevant vocabulary improved student achievement in relation to vocabulary</p> <p>-significant statistical differences at 5th grade level for incidental word learning</p> <p>-studies incorporating multiple exposures had good results, but this was not studied in isolation</p> <p>-multiple strategy instruction had positive effects</p> <p>- studies that used graphic organisers as part of instruction had positive effects</p>
Lawson-Adams, J.; Dickinson, D.K. (2020). Building lexical representations with nonverbal supports <i>Reading Research Quarterly</i> , 5(3) 603-622.				Preschool, to grade 2	<p>-gestures, pictures, and sounds can help support word learning as it provides students with multimodal access to vocabulary learning (Rowe et al., 2013; Tellier, 2008), particularly relevant to the learning of academic vocabulary, (Townsend, Filippini, Collins, & Biancarosa, 2012).</p> <p>-studies featuring songs were particularly effective at encouraging student engagement (Madsen, 1991; Schunk, 1999)</p> <p>- engaging young children in discussions about words enhanced their word knowledge (Beck & McKeown, 2007)</p>

<p>Sedgwick, A. & Stothard, J. (2018). A systematic review of school-based, mainstream oral language interventions for key stage 1 children <i>Support for Learning</i> 2018;33(4):360-387</p>	10			Lower primary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -studies that focused on shared reading found that both comprehension and vocabulary improved. -positive effects reported from embedded vocabulary instruction interventions where vocabulary was taught in context of a text using child friendly definitions -recommends extended vocabulary instruction over ‘embedded instruction’ which involves a brief discussion of new vocabulary -including morphological awareness task or phonics and orthographic tasks in the follow-up activities, during extended instruction, improves effectiveness of the vocabulary intervention -cumulative review of vocabulary knowledge is essential to ensure long-term word knowledge, with semantic review significantly more effective than embedded review at improving children’s word knowledge
<p>Swanson, E., Vaughn, S., Wanzek, J., Petscher, Y., Heckett, J., Cavaugh, C., Kraft, G., Tackett, K (2011). A synthesis of read-aloud interventions on early reading outcomes among preschool through third graders at risk for reading difficulties, <i>Journal of Learning Disabilities</i>, 44(4):396</p>	18			Preschool-grade 3	<p>Significant, positive effects on children's language, phonological awareness, print concepts, comprehension, and vocabulary outcomes were found from interventions that used dialogic reading; repeated reading of stories; story reading with limited questioning before, during, and/or after reading; computer-assisted story reading; and story reading with extended vocabulary activities.</p>
<p>Wright, T. S.& Cervetti, G. N. (2017). A systematic review of the research on vocabulary instruction that impacts text comprehension <i>Reading Research Quarterly</i>, 52(2):203-226</p>	36			Pre-k to 12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -teaching word meanings supports comprehension of text containing the same target words - instruction emphasizing active processing was more effective than definition- or dictionary usage in relation to vocabulary instruction. -limited evidence that explicit teaching of word meanings can improve overall reading comprehension -no empirical evidence that strategy instruction enhances generalized comprehension.

Wasik, B. A., Hindman, A. H. & Snell, E. K. (2016). Book reading and vocabulary development: A systematic review <i>Early Childhood Research Quarterly</i> , 37():39-57	30			3–6 years	-adult and child interaction during book reading is critical for vocabulary learning to occur. -Effects of interventions featuring book reading are modest -book reading should be considered an important part of a larger system of instruction to build vocabulary, including a range of other activities such as play-based learning
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Reading Fluency

Title of Article and Authors, Year of Publication	No. of studies	Effect sizes (If available)	Aspect of reading	Age range/ Grade	Findings
Hudson, A., Koh, Poh W., Moore, K., & Binks-Cantrell, E. (2020) Fluency Interventions for Elementary Students with Reading Difficulties: A Synthesis of Research from 2000-2019 <i>Education Sciences</i> 2020;10(3), 52	16	Wide variability across studies: no statistically significant gains for oral reading fluency to large effects found (ES = 0.01 to 1.18). Three studies: prosody outcomes large, significant effects [51,60,61]. Effect sizes for reading comprehension varied: no or negligible effects large effects on reading comprehension (ES = 0.07–2.59) Comprehension effect sizes larger than for oral reading fluency.		1 st to 8 th grade	-most studies focused on speed and rate aspects rather than prosody due to difficulties encountered in measuring this aspect of fluency -Effect sizes for rate and accuracy measures ranged from negligible to large (i.e., 0.01 to 1.18) and three studies found large effects for prosody outcomes. -Effect sizes for reading comprehension ranged between non-significant and large significant effects. -Repeated reading of text found to be effective to build up ORF of students with reading difficulties. - one-on-one interventions with a trained model of fluent word reading and accuracy were most effective -targeted fluency instruction can promote reading comprehension improvement as 75% of the studies were found to produce small to large effects on the oral reading fluency of students with reading difficulties and 50% of the studies had small to large effects on reading comprehension outcomes for these students, with the majority of interventions yielding moderate to large effect sizes across a variety of measures. Hence, fluency enhancement can be useful in interventions aimed at improving reading comprehension. - multifaceted interventions that include a variety of reading-related skills are more effective than those that focus on only one skill

Reading Instruction/Intervention					
Title of Article and Authors, Year of Publication	No. of studies	Effect sizes (If available)	Aspect of reading:	Age range / Grade	Findings
Hall, M. S., Burns & M. K. (2018) Meta-analysis of targeted small-group reading interventions. Journal of School Psychology, 66():54-66	26	moderate overall effect for small-group reading interventions (weighted $g = 0.54$). Interventions more effective if they targeted a specific skill ($g = 0.65$); as part of a comprehensive intervention program that addressed multiple skills ($g = 0.35$). small correlation between intervention effects and group size ($r = 0.21$) and duration ($r = 0.11$); Small-group interventions: a larger median effect size ($g = 0.64$) for elementary-aged students VS middle or high school ($g = 0.20$), but the two confidence		Primary and secondary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -recommends small-group reading interventions in order to achieve positive effect for students. -targeted reading interventions to students in small-groups through a multi-tiered system of support enhances reading skills -recommends that teachers be trained in delivering small group interventions as effect sizes were affected by facilitator expertise. -small-group storybook reading interventions were an effective method for increasing young students' vocabulary in a short amount of time. -groups of less than five students were more effective than groups with five or more students -elementary school students' gains were over three times as large as the one for secondary students, but the confidence intervals for the two estimates of effect did overlap. This finding highlights the importance of early intervention and supports providing additional small-group intervention for students displaying early signs of experiencing reading difficulties providing additional small-group intervention for students displaying early signs of experiencing reading difficulties.

		intervals overlapped			
Puzio, K. & Colby, G. T. (2013). Cooperative learning and literacy: A meta-analytic erview. <i>Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness</i> 2013;6(4):339-360	18	The overall weighted mean effect sizes ranged from 0.16 to 0.22 ($p < .01$) with more than 94% of the point estimates being positive.		Grades 2 through 12.	-significantly higher literacy achievement scores when instructional interventions utilized cooperative and collaborative activity structures. - difficult to judge the extent of the effect as cooperative or collaborative learning was always one of multiple intervention components -a core component of effective literacy interventions, particularly at the elementary level. -positive effects for students who initially had the lowest literacy achievement, highlights the usefulness of cooperative and collaborative approaches for a mixed ability grouping within a class -No studies on guided reading
Puzio, K., Colby, G. T.; Algeo-Nichols, D. (2020). Differentiated Literacy Instruction: Boondoggle or Best Practice? <i>Review of Educational Research</i> , 90(4):459-498	18	Overall mean effect size (g) was +0.13 ($p = .002$) with 88% of the individual point estimates being positive letter-word ($g = +0.20, p = .014$) and writing outcomes ($g = +0.96, p < .001$)		k-12	-differentiated literacy instruction is an effective practice at the elementary school level. The most successful programs took very different approaches to differentiation, including -the use of individualization, student choice, and an alternate curriculum were found to be the most successful approaches -no experimental or quasi-experimental studies on guided reading -assessing and analysing formal student literacy data led to successful outcomes
Reynolds, M. Wheldall, K. & Madelaine, A. (2011) What recent reviews tell us about the efficacy of reading interventions for struggling readers in the early years of schooling, <i>International Journal of Disability, Development and Education</i> ,	6			Pre-k- 1 st grade	The National Reading Panel (NICHD, 2000).; -Phonemic awareness instruction was found to be highly effective in improving children’s reading. It is most effective when it features explicit and systematic teaching that links the manipulation of phonemes with the associated letters, and when instruction is limited to the teaching of only one or two phoneme manipulation skills. It is most effectively taught in small groups, for sessions of approximately 30 minutes in

58:3, 257-286, DOI: 10.1080/1034912X.2011.5984062 011					<p>duration. Research indicates that 20 hours of training time is most effective. Phonemic awareness should be taught in preschool and kindergarten rather than in older grades.</p> <p>Critiques of NRP's findings about the role and teaching of phonics after reanalysis of the data (Camilli, Kim, & Vargas, 2008; Camilli et al., 2003; Garan, 2001; Hammill & Swanson, 2006) included a smaller effect sizes for a systematic approach over a non-systematic approach (d = 0.24) compared to the NRP's findings of d = 0.41) and insufficient evidence to say that, in general, students have better results when given phonics instruction in comparison with students given reading instruction without phonics. They also found that phonics instruction efficacy was limited to the improvement of decoding skills.</p> <p>Paper also reviews findings from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The National Inquiry into the Teaching of Literacy (NITL) ● The Independent Review of the Teaching of Early Reading: ● What Works Clearinghouse Review of Beginning Reading Programmes ● Review of Effective Programmes for Struggling Readers: Slavin et al. (2009) --- ● Hattie's Synthesis of Meta-analyses Related to Achievement:
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Research on Pedagogies/Approaches to Writing

Title of Article and Authors, Year of Publication	No. of studies	Effect sizes (If available)	Foci of Article	Age range /	Findings (also refer to definitions of literacy/numeracy, as used in article/report)
Graham, S. (2019). Changing how writing Is taught.	Narrative review of	n/a	Factors influencing writing	Elementary/ secondary	Writing is linked to success in school, work, personal life. Many students do not acquire writing skills naturally. They don't receive the instruction they need/deserve.

<p><i>Review of Research in Education, 43(1), 277–303.</i></p>	<p>writing research: 28 survey, observation, mixed method studies involving the writing practices of more than 7,000 teachers US, NZ Europe, China Sth. America</p>		<p>pedagogy and quality of instruction</p>		<p>Factors inhibiting good writing instruction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall picture from the 28 studies reviewed: writing instruction in most classrooms is not sufficient. • Daily instructional time insufficient (Brindle et al, 2016; Graham et al., 2014) • Though many teachers are aware of effective teaching practices/adaptations/not used often • Infrequent opportunities to engage in different types of writing (Brindle et al., 2016; Kiuahara et al., 2009; Koko, 2016) • Notable absence of digital tools for writing though (Freedman et al., 2016) • At primary level: over-emphasis on grammar, handwriting/spelling; little emphasis on writing processes e.g. planning/revising (Cutler & Graham, 2008; Dockrell et al., 2016; Rietdijk et al., 2018) • At post-primary level: writing tasks used to support learning across disciplines: mostly fill in blanks, note-taking or one sentence responses rather than writing as composing (e.g. Gillespie et al. 2014; Ray et al., 2016)
<p>Slavin, R.E., Lake, C., Inns, A., Baye, A., Dacht, D., & Haslam, J. (2019). A quantitative synthesis of research on writing approaches in grades 2 to 12. Best Evidence Encyclopaedia (BEE)</p> <p><i>Center for Research and Reform in Education, Johns Hopkins University. Baltimore, MD</i></p>	<p>14 studies included 11 extensive points to detail inclusion in study over two pages, further exclusion criteria in document</p>	<p>Student achievement effect: positive on average in all categories (Size=+0.18), similar outcomes for: writing process (ES=+0.17); those using cooperative learning</p>	<p>Research on outcomes of writing programs</p>	<p>Grades 2-12</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty with inflation of effect sizes in many studies • Findings detailed under individual programs, mean ES shared across three categories <p>Writing Approaches Explored:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Writing Process Models • Self-Regulated Strategy Development SRSD • 6+1 Trait Writing Model • Cooperative Learning • Writing Wings • Student Team Writing • Collaborative Strategic Reading (CSR) • Expert 21 • Programs Integrating Reading and Writing:

		(ES=+0.16); on interactions between reading/writin g (ES=+0.19).			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The College-Ready Writers Program (CRWP) • Pathway • Philosophy for Children (P4C) • Academic Language Instruction for All Students (ALIAS) • The Expository Reading Writing Course (ERWC)
<p>McMaster, K. L., Kunkel, A., Shin, J., Jung, P.-G., & Lembke, E. (2018).</p> <p>Early writing intervention: A best evidence synthesis.</p> <p><i>Journal of Learning Disabilities, 51</i>(4), 363–380.</p>	<p>25 studies met inclusion criteria</p> <p>Group and single subject designs</p> <p>Inclusion criteria Drew on previous reviews as well (Graham et al, 2012 below)</p>	<p>Among group design studies, mean effects (Hedge’s <i>g</i>) ranged from 0.19 to 1.17 for measures of writing quantity from 0.17 to 0.85 for measures of writing quality</p>	<p>Purpose: to identify promising interventions aligned with theoretical model of writing development, targeting three components of early writing: transcription, text generation, and self-regulation.</p>	<p>K-3rd LD populations</p>	<p>Conceptual framework Conceptualization of early writing: based on theoretical model of early writing (Hayes & Flower, 1980)</p> <p>Findings Transcription Explicit systematic instruction in handwriting and spelling not only improves student performance on these specific skills but can also lead to improved outcomes in terms of written composition quantity and quality</p> <p>Only one study examined text generation exclusively with only one student with autism, limits conclusions that can be drawn about interventions focusing primarily on text generation; studies were generally high quality and provided ample evidence that providing students with text generation and self-regulation strategies through SRSD leads to improved writing composition (contradicts Slavin et al. above)</p> <p>Implications for practice. explicit transcription instruction (handwriting and spelling) leads to improved writing composition; foundational skills–based instruction might be needed for students who struggle with writing, to free up cognitive attention needed to engage in the more complex writing tasks that are currently required in school. These skills are often underemphasized in state standards and popular curricula</p>

<p>Koster, M., Tribushinina, E., Jong, P. F. de, & Bergh, H. van den. (2015). Teaching children to write: A meta-analysis of writing intervention research. <i>Journal of Writing Research</i>, 7(2), 249–274. https://doi.org/10.17239/jowr-2015.07.02.2</p>	<p>Meta-analysis of experimental and quasi-experimental writing intervention studies aimed at students in the upper elementary grades 32 writing intervention studies</p>	<p>Average ES 10 intervention 5 statistically significant Most effective: goal setting (ES= 2.03), strategy instruction (.96), text structure instruction (.76), peer assistance (.59), feedback (.88) Overall ES .72</p>	<p>Identifying effective instructional practices for teaching composition to students in the upper grades of elementary school</p>	<p>Grades 4-6 Regular school setting</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Netherlands a majority of students don't attain desired level of writing skills; end elementary school • lack of progress between grades 4 and 6 • weaker writers at a disadvantage in secondary school • Time /attention to writing instruction limited/Lack of adequate training for teachers <p>Findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two negative effects- grammar instruction and process approach • Goal setting by far most effective intervention <p>Implications for Teaching:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Writing curriculum: include goal setting, strategy instruction, text structure instruction, feedback and peer interaction. • Setting process goals, such as learning to apply a certain strategy, was highly effective. • Strategy instruction was more effective when combined with teaching self-regulatory skills • Specific, targeted interventions, such as explicit instruction in applying strategies or how to structure a text were particularly effective for elementary
<p>Graham, S., McKeown, D., Kiuahara, S., & Harris, K. R. (2012). A meta-analysis of writing instruction for students in the elementary grades. <i>Journal of Educational Psychology</i>, 104(4), 879–896.</p>	<p>115 studies</p>	<p>calculated an average weighted ES for 13 writing interventions</p>		<p>Grades 1-3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30 studies: interventions students in Grades 1–3 studies, about 27%: SRSD; 27% addressed transcription skills, • remainder addressed a variety of multicomponent, word-processing, and peer mediated interventions. • Interventions yielding strongest effects in Grades 1–3 included strategy instruction (effect size range = 0.25–1.89), text structure instruction (0.33–0.94), teaching transcription skills (0.12–2.40), prewriting activities (0.56–0.88). • McMaster et al. SRSD was identified as a strong intervention. Findings converge with the overall SRSD research (conducted with a wider range of grade levels) indicating that SRSD can be considered “evidence based” (Baker et al., 2009).

<p>Graham, S., & Sandmel, K. (2011). The Process Writing Approach: A Meta-Analysis. <i>Journal of Educational Research, 104</i>(6), 396–407. ERIC.</p>	<p>Meta-analysis of 29 experimental and quasi-experimental studies.</p>	<p><i>statistically significant, but relatively modest improvement in the overall quality of writing (average weighted effect size [ES] = 0.34).</i></p>	<p>process writing</p>	<p>Grades 1-12</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> improved overall quality of writing in general education classes. mean average weighted ES: a random-effects model was 0.34. did not improve struggling or at-risk students' overall writing quality (average weighted ES 0.29) or enhance students' motivation (ES 0.19) Writing quality related to professional development, grade, scoring reliability, genre assessed; ES unrelated to study quality advocates of process writing instruction integrate other effective writing practices into this approach. High-quality research is needed to examine the effectiveness of the most promising hybrids.
Research on Grammar, Spelling, Morphology					
Title of Article and Authors, Year of Publication	No. studies reviewed	Effect sizes (If available)	Foci of Article	Age range /	Findings
<p>Jagaiah, T., Olinghouse, N. G., & Kearns, D. M. (2020). Syntactic Complexity Measures: Variation by Genre, Grade-Level, Students' Writing Abilities, and Writing Quality. <i>Reading and Writing: An Interdisciplinary Journal, 33</i>(10), 2577–2638. eric.</p>	<p>Systematic review synthesizing 36 studies.</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Syntactic Complexity Measures (SCM) Relationship between SCMs, writing quality and genre. Examination of how SCMs vary by (a) genre, (b) grade level, (c) writing ability, and</p>	<p>K-12</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students in lower elementary grades expected to write in various genres using sophisticated vocabulary/ sentence structures. No formally accepted definition of syntactic complexity-abstract concept. Studies have focused on developing various SCMs to analyse complexity. <p>Details of Review</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 48 SCMs identified in 36 studies. Six categories: <i>T-units and sentences, clauses, phrases, words, combined SCMs, other SCMs.</i> <p>Findings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Different T-unit definitions across studies made it difficult to compare results from different studies Findings not conclusive. Difficult to compare most studies generally showed higher use of SCMs among students with higher writing abilities.

			(d) writing quality.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shortcoming leads to inconsistent findings is <u>lack of a single comprehensive study</u> examining a large number of SCMs simultaneously using a large data set. • students mature, can construct more complex sentence structures- <i>is there is a need to provide sentence construction instruction in writing classroom.</i> • Competence in constructing longer/syntactically complex sentences does not necessarily translate to students' ability to generate ideas and communicate effectively in connected writing.
<p>Myhill, D., & Watson, A. (2014).</p> <p>The role of grammar in the writing curriculum: A review of the literature.</p> <p><i>Child Language Teaching and Therapy</i>, 30(1), 41–62.</p>	<p>Review of literature on the teaching of grammar</p> <p>Focus on these studies in more detail Bateman and Zidonis (1966), Elley et al. (1975, 1979) and Fogel and Ehri (2000). Sherard et al., (2012) but others examined.</p>	N/A	<p>The role of grammar in the curriculum, does the teaching of grammar impact on writing? Prescriptive and descriptive approaches to teaching grammar</p>	<p>Primary school to high school, university level mentioned in one study</p>	<p>Background: History of grammar teaching over past 50 years is one of contestation, debate and dissent- Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) and work of Halliday- meaning-oriented theorisation of grammar, exploring relationship between text and context. language as a social semiotic system.</p> <p>Grammar Teaching Widespread belief that teachers' grammatical knowledge needs to be richer and more substantive than the grammar they need to teach students. Argument that teachers who understand grammatical forms may be better placed to support developing writers (Andrews, 2005).</p> <p>Summary</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Signs of an emerging consensus that grammar may be important in developing learners' understanding of how language works, how grammar choices are significant in shaping and constructing meaning. • More important to know how than to know what. • Grammar as a choice, a repertoire of infinite possibilities (Myhill et al., 2011). • More well-designed studies needed in this area

<p>Graham, S., & Santangelo, T. (2014).</p> <p>Does Spelling Instruction Make Students Better Spellers, Readers, and Writers? A Meta-Analytic Review.</p> <p><i>Reading and Writing: An Interdisciplinary Journal</i>, 27(9), 1703–1743. ERIC.</p>	<p>53 studies Meta-analysis</p> <p>Experimental and quasi-experimental studies</p>	<p>58 effect sizes: performance compared to no/unrelated instruction (ES = 0.54); or informal/incidental approaches to improving spelling (ES = 0.43); Increasing formal instruction (ES = 0.70); maintained over time (ES = 0.53) generalized to spelling in writing (ES = 0.94); Improved phonological awareness (ES = 0.51) reading skills (ES = 0.44)</p>	<p>Exploring the impact of formally teaching spelling on spelling, phonological awareness, reading, and writing performance</p>	<p>K- 12</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spelling important to reading and writing/exerts toll on writers, especially developing writers. • disagreement about how spelling competence is best acquired-caught/ taught approach Both approaches supported empirically. “Caught”- (• Meta-analysis explores 8 research questions. <p>Summary:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meta-analysis consistently found that formal spelling instruction improved students’ spelling performance- strong support for directly and systematically teaching students how to spell. • Primary grade teachers should continue to explicitly and systematically teach spelling; teachers in upper elementary grades should place more emphasis on such instruction; schools should consider if such instruction should be extended into middle school. • Findings dispute idea spelling skills and knowledge learned through formal instruction do not generalise to students’ writing (Graham, 1999). • Effects were not obtained in six studies: Hypothesised that writing/ instruction occurred infrequently or not at all for students • Future analyses of the spelling instruction literature needs to examine if specific spelling interventions produce different results.
<p>Goodwin, A. P., & Ahn, S. (2013).</p> <p>A Meta-Analysis of Morphological Interventions in</p>	<p>30 studies</p>	<p>Overall effect (0.32 weighted effect size)</p>	<p>Effects of morphological study on</p>	<p>Pre-school to 9th Grade</p>	<p>How morphological knowledge relates to literacy tasks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through morphemic analysis, students can infer the pronunciation, meanings, and spellings of many words beyond those taught

<p>English: Effects on Literacy Outcomes for School-Age Children.</p> <p><i>Scientific Studies of Reading</i>, 17(4), 257–285.</p>		<p>significant moderate intervention effects on morphological knowledge (d = 0.44); phonological awareness (d = 0.48); vocabulary (d = 0.34), decoding (d = 0.59); spelling (d = 0.30) but not on reading comprehension or fluency.</p>	<p>language and literacy</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • After third grade, 60 to 80% of words in texts are derived words (Nagy & Anderson, 1984). • Instructional time/ setting/ variables/ focus differ across research • Morphological demands differ across stages of school- simple demands in early elementary, increasing in middle school and increased demands in high school. Increased understanding leads to ability to access more complex texts. <p>Findings pertinent to spelling</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results suggest statistically significant larger effects for preschool and early elementary students through second grade followed by middle school and upper elementary students. • Moderate effects shown for upper elementary/middle school. Greatest effects noted for ELLs, poor readers and spellers, and children with learning disabilities- but differences not statistically meaningful. • Various types of instruction support literacy achievement, including instruction that builds morphological knowledge by identifying, segmenting, and building with morphemes; teaching students affix and root meanings; teaching morphological patterns that support spelling; and teaching students to analyse compound words (see Goodwin, Lipsky, & Ahn, 2012, for more details).
<p>Kent, S. C., & Wanzek, J. (2016).</p> <p>The Relationship Between Component Skills and Writing Quality and Production Across Developmental Levels.</p> <p><i>Review of Educational Research</i>, 86(2), 570–601.</p>	<p>38 studies Publication date 1988-2013</p>	<p>Each of the component skills demonstrates a weak to moderate positive relationship to outcomes assessing writing quality (rs =</p>	<p>Correlation between component skills/ writing outcomes. Relationships between handwriting fluency, spelling, reading,</p>	<p>5-18 years of age</p>	<p>Component processes in writing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Writing is a complex task requiring considerable knowledge and cognitive effort. • Shift towards focus on both process and product since Flower and Hayes (1980). • Role of transcription skills and working memory highlighted <p>Summary and Implications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderate, significant correlations between individual component skills/students' writing quality/generally weak relationships with amount of writing produced.

		.33–.49) and the amount students write (rs = .20–.48).	and oral language and students' quality of writing and writing production		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relationship between reading achievement/writing production stronger for students in primary grades. • Quality of writing most strongly correlated with transcription skills (handwriting fluency/spelling) and with reading achievement. • Development of proficient transcription skills may free up cognitive resources for higher-level processes. • Explicit instruction in handwriting recommended, beginning in kindergarten (Graham, Bollinger, et al., 2012; Graham, McKeown, et al., 2012).
Research on Handwriting					
Title of Article and Authors, Year of Publication	No. of studies	Effect sizes (Ifavailable)	Foci of Article	Age range /	Findings
Patiño, J. F., Calixto, A. L., Chiappe, A., & Almenarez, F. T. (2020). ICT-Driven Writing and Motor Skills: A Review. <i>International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education</i> , 12(5), 489–498.	180 documents		Review of literature : handwriting, ICT and motor skill development		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handwriting supports development of writing skills/contributes to fluency. Early writing requires good coordination: motor, perceptive, cognitive processes. • Considerable individual differences among pre-schoolers in emergent literacy; Early alphabet knowledge a key factor in later reading and writing, • Writing is one of the biggest problems for children with disabilities in school. <p>Writing and ICT Skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICT facilitates writing processes: Positive aspects: erasing/correcting without leaving trace; writing ideas; making comments/notes in the same file • Word processors as complementary aid: improves basic writing skills: graph recognition, directionality • Facilitates "collaborative writing", • Supports future learning of more complex knowledge/ personal reflection, thought, creativity • Complements other modes of communication: multimodal texts.
Limpo, T., & Graham, S. (2020).			Automacity and explicit and		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Putting words on paper imposes heavy demands on young writers' limited capacity of working memory: attending to writing letters leaves little attention to monitor and evaluate

<p>The Role of Handwriting Instruction in Writers' Education.</p> <p><i>British Journal of Educational Studies</i>, 68(3), 311–329. ERIC.</p>			<p>systematic teaching of handwriting</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital composing devices used in more and more schools, handwriting is still highly valued/needed ● Handwriting: complex neuromotor skill encompassing numerous cognitive and motor processes ● Increasing research evidence shows a relationship between handwriting skill and writing achievement throughout schooling ● Poor handwriting skills influence readers' judgements about the quality of the presented ideas as well as about the writing ability of the writer. ● Slow writers: difficulty record ideas at pace at which they are able to generate them in their minds; low writing achievement, avoidance behaviours/writing apprehension /low self-efficacy <p>Assessment and teaching of handwriting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Legibility, fluency accuracy and speed. ● Gender difference: girls achieve higher levels of handwriting fluency than boys. ● Variation in time spent teaching writing: ranging from 2 minutes to 60 minutes daily in US. <p>Evidence-based practices to promote handwriting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Instructional programs resulted in improvements in handwriting fluency and written composition; Students with/without handwriting difficulties benefit from explicit instruction ● No empirical evidence supporting teaching of motor skills or use of other types of sensory-motor training without explicit handwriting practice as a way to improve handwriting ● Kindergarten/Grades 1–3:instruction should include distributed practice/a total of 50-100 minutes weekly ● Initial stages of handwriting instruction should target the name and the form of each alphabet letter ● Time to write frequently is an effective method for promoting handwriting legibility/fluency; five hr of HW training, students' fluency increased
<p>Feng, L., Lindner, A., Ji, X. R., & Malatesha Joshi, R. (2019).</p>	<p>Study 1: 19 studies</p>	<p>Study 1: 59 effect sizes</p>	<p>Handwriting fluency and</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Handwriting fluency is positively associated with: length/quality of compositions: beginning writers allows writer to devote working memory to higher-level writing

<p>The roles of handwriting and keyboarding in writing: a meta-analytic review.</p> <p><i>Reading and Writing</i>, 32(1), 33–63. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-017-9749-x</p>	<p>Study 2: 7 documents</p>		<p>writing; what other factors affect relationship</p> <p>Study 2: relationship between handwriting and keyboarding</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of handwriting fluency, linked to cognitive demands for young children: they write more simply and do not participate in writing processes (e.g. planning/revising) ● Difficulties may lead to diminished self-efficacy; lower academic achievement; behavioural problems <p>The difference/similarities between handwriting keyboarding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Both require the cognitive ability to retrieve the appropriate letters and hold them in memory. ● Keyboarding requires the writer to visually recognize and select the appropriate letters on the keyboard. ● Overall, despite the widespread use of technology in classrooms, handwriting is still critical for students’ writing development/should be explicitly taught. ● Handwriting and keyboarding both significantly positively associated with the development of writing
<p>Fancher, L. A., Priestley-Hopkins, D. A., & Jeffries, L. M. (2018).</p> <p>Handwriting Acquisition and Intervention: A Systematic Review.</p> <p><i>Journal of Occupational Therapy, Schools & Early Intervention</i>, 11(4), 454–473. ERIC.</p>	<p>8 handwriting group intervention studies and 7 experimental group studies</p>		<p>Impact of early writing in preschool and effectiveness of handwriting interventions</p>	<p>Kindergarten - second grade (preschool to age 7)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Elementary students benefit: handwriting is explicitly taught/Legibility improves with sufficient practice. ● Wide variation in formal handwriting instruction in elementary school: no instruction to direct instruction to manualized handwriting programs ● Effective occupational therapy interventions must include adequate handwriting practice. Handwriting in older preschool children contributes to letter recognition ● Self-generated letter writing/approximation of letters/symbols resulted in neural activation of networks associated with known reading/visual perception networks; associated with better letter or symbol recognition when compared to other sensori-motor activities such as typing, tracing, passively viewing/saying the letter name out loud. ● Greater neural activation occurred when actively writing cursive letters; Writing allows for longer durations of learning than merely seeing or saying letters. ● More research needed: to determine age for formal instruction; instructional pedagogy for pre-K, duration of instruction, and monitoring of all aspects of handwriting

<p>Santangelo, T., & Graham, S. (2016). Comprehensive Meta-Analysis of Handwriting Instruction. <i>Educational Psychology Review</i>, 28(2), 225–265.</p>	<p>80 experiments described in 76 unique documents</p>		<p>HW instruction - effects on legibility and fluency, student's writing skills, effectiveness of specific methods to teach HW</p>	<p>k -12 students</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Handwriting: bias readers' judgments re ideas in a text/impact other writing processes/legibility or spelling correctness, influence readers' judgments about quality of ideas in a written text; Speed continues to increase at least until grade 9 ● Children experiencing HW difficulties avoid writing/ develop mind set they can't write/boys greater risk than girls ● HW is best taught vs. caught: systematic/explicit older students showed greater improvement in fluency when instructed, compared to younger students ● Individualized HW instruction: Legibility: positive results reported in seven experiments; level of competence in HW may be needed before fluency gains can be maximized. ● Amount of instruction ranged from 22.5 to 480 min. Students receiving 10h or more of instruction made greater legibility gains than students who were provided 8 h or less. ● No support for teaching motor skills as a way to improve HW performance.
<p>Schwellnus, Cameron & Carnahan. 2012. Which to Choose: Manuscript or Cursive Handwriting? A Review of the Literature. <i>Journal of Occupational Therapy, Schools, & Early Intervention</i>, 5(3–4), 248–258.</p>	<p>69</p>		<p>Manuscript VS Cursive Writing</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No difference in children's reading skill regardless of whether manuscript or disjoined cursive is taught; benefits of manuscript over cursive: evidence does not seem to exist ● Student's grip on pencil not found to be link to either good/bad quality writing; Motoric complexity of letters determined by level of dexterity of finger movements in completing letters/Wrist/finger movements must be coordinated to form letters in both cursive and manuscript.. ● Similar but different challenges associated with both forms; no appear to be strong evidence to support the choice of one over the other; some form of handwriting beneficial for children to learn even with advances in technology regardless of the format of writing, more structured instruction time and increased practice is needed and that remediation programs are successful when they are altered to suit the age of the children.